

CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D3.2 Guidelines for the sustainability and resilience of inland water transport and logistics

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

Document summary information

Grant Agreement No	101069838	Acronym	CRISTAL
Full Title	Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways		
Start Date	01/09/2022	Duration	36 months
Project URL	http://www.cristal-project.eu/		
Deliverable	Guidelines for the sustainability and resilience of IWT&L		
Work Package	WP3		
Contractual due date	31/03/2023	Actual submission date	31/03/2023
Type	R	Dissemination Level	PU
Lead Participant	SOGESCA		

Revision history

Version	Issue Date	Complete %	Changes	Contributor(s)
V0.1	06/02/2023	10%	TOC finalized and approved	Rose Ortolani Paola Bottega
V0.2	16/03/2023	35%	Input from the French pilot	VNF
V0.3	17/03/2023	40%	First draft version of the document (Chapters 5, 6 and 7)	Rose Ortolani Paola Bottega
V0.4	23/03/2023	50%	Input regarding sub-chapter 7.5	Certh
V0.5	23/03/2023	55%	Input from the Italian pilot (IV)	IV
V0.6	24/03/2023	65%	Input from the Polish and Italian (AIPO) pilot	UnGda AIPO
V0.7	24/03/2023	95%	Final editing and submission for the QA peer-review process	Rose Ortolani Paola Bottega
V0.8	29/03/2023	97%	Peer-review	VNF
V0.9	29/03/2023	98%	Peer-review	Fraunhofer
V1	31/03/2023	100%	Final revision based on reviewer's comments & submission to the EC	Rose Ortolani Paola Bottega
V1.1	31/03/2023	100%	Final verification	Marta Cudziło (L-PIT)

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
AOS	Asset, Operation and System
BCM	Business Continuity Management
BCMS	Business Continuity Management System
BIA	Business Impact Analysis
CC	Climate Change
CO₂e	Carbon dioxide equivalent
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Green House Gases
GWP	Global Warming Potential
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
IWT	Inland Water Transport
IWT&L	Inland Water Transport and Logistic
IWW	Inland Water Ways
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LULUCF	Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry
MBCO	Minimum Business Continuity Objective
MTPD	Maximum Tolerable Period of Disruption
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
PIANC	Permanent International Association of Navigational Congresses

RCPs	Representative Concentration Pathways
RIS	River Information System
RTO	Recovery Time Objective
RVA	Risk and Vulnerability Assessment
SCMS	Synchromodal Corridor Management System
SECAP	Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan
SR	Social Responsibility
UNO	United Nations Organization
USD	United States dollar
WP	Work Package

Disclaimer

The content of the publication herein is the sole responsibility of the publishers and it does not necessarily represent the views expressed by the European Commission or its services.

While the information contained in the documents is believed to be accurate, the authors(s) or any other participant in the CRISTAL consortium make no warranty of any kind with regard to this material including, but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose.

Neither the CRISTAL Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be responsible or liable in negligence or otherwise howsoever in respect of any inaccuracy or omission herein.

Without derogating from the generality of the foregoing neither the CRISTAL Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be liable for any direct or indirect or consequential loss or damage caused by or arising from any information advice or inaccuracy or omission herein.

Copyright message

© CRISTAL Consortium, 2022-2025. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of contents

Document summary information	1
Revision history	2
List of abbreviations	3
1. Executive Summary	7
1.1. Introduction	7
1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs	8
1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	10
2. Guidelines objectives and stakeholders addressed	12
2.1. Objectives	12
2.2. Stakeholders' addressees of the identified guidelines	13
3. Drivers leading the sustainable development of IWT L system	14
4. Management systems standards for individual organizations (public and private entities) as reliability boosters	17
5. Supporting tools for public bodies to increase their resilience to natural or human-made disruptive events	19
5.1. Resilience indicators for public authorities and infrastructure operators (e.g., ports)	19
5.2. Covenant of Majors plans (Sustainable Energy and Climate Adaptation Plan - SECAP) for climate change hazards identification and impact on the different municipality sectors.....	23
6. Supporting tools for private companies to increase their sustainability	26
6.1. Corporate sustainability and accountability on environmental, social and governance issues	27
6.2. Tools for mitigation actions	31
7. Tools for Business continuity.....	39
7.1. Asset management.....	42
7.2. Business continuity management.....	44
7.3. Emergency and incident management	47
7.4. Climate change adaptation and its planning.....	50
7.5. Synchromodal corridor management system	59
8. Conclusions	63
9. References	64

10. Appendices	65
Annex I - Glossary of key adaptation terms	65
Annex II – Questionnaire answers from CRISTAL river pilots.....	69
11. List of tables	80
12. List of figures.....	80

1. Executive Summary

The present deliverable details a new approach to enhance Inland Waterways Transport and Logistic network management, acting on the organizations belonging to the system itself and other relevant stakeholders. The proposed tools aim at improving reliability, sustainability and resilience of IWT&L system organizations that are trying to improve their attractiveness.

The following deliverable can be considered a pre-requisite for the end-users of the Synchronodal Corridor Management System, as it provides many of the features required, with a synergistic effect brought by cooperation and collaboration.

The core of the deliverable is introduced by an overview of international sustainability drivers, such as UNO sustainable development goals and different European directives and strategies, in particular on the new ESG (Environment, social and governance) theory that is leading to a sustainable process.

The listed operational tools mainly come from ISO standards, as they are internationally acknowledged and suitable for organizations of any type and any size. In this sense, these guidelines can be downscaled from any organization considering its specific framework and objectives.

Climate change resilience and adaptation actions are mainly tailored on-stakeholders (public and private) using and managing the river infrastructure and to municipalities crossed by the water way.

A questionnaire has finally been delivered to the CRISTAL river pilots, to assess their awareness and current practices related to the topics addressed in the guidelines. It appears that the situation in the pilots varies a lot between them.

1.1. Introduction

The main goal of the present document is providing individual organizations belonging to IWT&L networks with tools to boost their sustainability and resilience towards natural and man-made disruptions, improving their own accountability and the attractiveness of the whole IWT&L network.

This document aims to give regulatory framework to support the development and the implementation of the innovations proposed in CRISTAL project.

It contributes to achieve CRISTAL main goals such as reliability improvement and an ensured IWT&L capacity even during extreme events. In this sense, the technological innovations developed in other WPs come with a new/upgraded organizational approach for individual organizations, entailed in this document, to prepare them to accept and exploit these new technologies.

The tools described in this document principally come from international standards and references. They are addressed to CRISTAL pilot's stakeholders and to IWT&L users. Keeping this in mind, the guidelines are

quite generic and are not specific to the waterway context, to let individual organizations tailor them on their specific needs and context.

After a preliminary part, specific tools for public and private organizations are described in chapter 5 and 6, respectively. They are foreseen in European directives and initiatives (i.e., CSRD Directive and Covenant of Mayors Initiative) and from standards aligned to European mitigation and decarbonization plans (i.e., Green New Deal and 2050 long term strategy).

The core part of the guidelines addresses the complex topic of Business Continuity, a critical issue in the field of transport and logistics.

A series of specific topics as asset management, business management, emergency management and climate change adaptation have been examined and put together to create a global all-hazard approach to natural and man-made disruptions.

Information about the current awareness and practices on river pilots have been addressed by an assessment questionnaire in Annex II.

The guidelines implementation will be performed within T7.3 of WP7.

The main content of the deliverable was drafted by SOGESCA with a contribution of CERTH for the paragraph describing the SCMS (7.5) and the pilots for the baseline assessment.

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

The purpose of this section is to provide an overview of the alignment of the document to the formal deliverable and corresponding task descriptions included in the GA and thus help the deliverable owners and the reviewers to conclude on the level of achievement of the deliverable/task goals.

Table 1 Alignment of D3.2 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable and task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D3.2 Guidelines for the sustainability and resilience of IWT&L</i>	<i>The guidelines will be based on the ISO 22301 Business continuity management systems, ISO 37123, Sustainable cities and communities – Indicators for resilient cities, ISO/TS</i>	<i>The guidelines will be found in the following chapters: 5. Public bodies supporting tools, 6. Private companies</i>	<i>The guidelines objectives and addressees have been identified in chapter 2. The general legal boundary is developed in chapter 3 (Drivers leading the</i>

	<p>22375:2018 <i>Security and resilience — Guidelines for complexity assessment process, ISO 1406x series for assessing and verifying GHG emissions, ISO 14090 Managing the impact of climate change, ISO 22320:2018 Emergency management — Guidelines for incident management, ISO 55001 Asset management, ISO 14001 Environmental quality management, ISO 50001 Energy Management System, ISO 26000 social accountability, "Taxonomy" Regulation EU 852/2020, Dir. CE 95/2014 Corporate sustainability reporting on the social and environmental impacts of their activities, EC TAXONOMY.</i></p>	<p><i>supporting tools and 7. Tools for Business continuity</i></p>	<p><i>development of the IWT&L System).</i></p> <p><i>The determination of some rules and guidelines to increase resilience and reliability of organisations is in chapter 4 (Management systems Standards for individual organizations - public and private entities- as resilience and reliability booster).</i></p> <p><i>In Chapters 5 (Public bodies supporting tools), 6 (Private company supporting tools) and 7 (Tools for Business continuity), will be presented some specific guidelines to achieve the Objectives identified in Chapter 2. Chapter 7 is focused on the stakeholders' services-users of the synchromodal corridor management system.</i></p>
TASKS			
<p>Task 3.2 Organizational approach to enhance the Inland Waterways Transport & Logistic (IWT&L) network systems management according to climate change</p>	<p><i>The solutions foreseen in WP3 will be enhanced by the implementation of climate change mitigation and adaptation international standards and EU policies, and the creation of a coherent organizational framework covering:</i></p> <p><i>(1) Stakeholder relationship management (e.g., Quadruple-Helix) to achieve</i></p>	<p><i>Part 2 with point a and b can be found in Chapters 4, 5, 6 and 7.</i></p>	<p><i>Chapters 4, 5, 6, and 7 will develop guidelines for resilience towards climate change and man-made disruptions respectively for public bodies, public companies participating in the IWT&L System in particular for the services users of the SCMS (in Chapter 7).</i></p>

<p>mitigation and resilience management international standards and EU policies</p>	<p><i>common understanding of basic management requirements and procedures (reference ISO-TS 22375) for the purposes of sustainability and resilience of IWT&L network systems (cooperation with WP4).</i></p> <p><i>(2) Management of individual organizations through reference guidelines for defining organizational models/plans for adoption in WP7-9 (Pilots), mainly based on:</i></p> <p><i>(a) Reference guidelines for companies (i.e., ISO 14090, NFRD Directive 95/2014).</i></p> <p><i>(b) Reference guideline for public bodies.</i></p> <p><i>(c) Capitalizing activities to involve stakeholders to support the synergies between SCMS and the existing/ongoing organizational framework with reference to WP1, WP2, WP4, WP5, WP6 and WP10 (i.e., at least 10 companies and 5 bodies will be involved from WP7).</i></p>		
--	--	--	--

1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The present report is divided into eight chapters.

Chapter 1 includes the executive summary along with the introductory section, the description of the document structure and the justification of the document alignment to the GA requirements.

Chapter 2 states objectives and stakeholders addressed by the present guidelines. Chapters 3 and 4 shortly describe the international drivers for sustainable development and a review of management system standards common parts.

Chapter 5 describes resilience tools for municipalities crossed by a water way, that can be affected by the water level in the river and for authorities and regulators involved in different ways in river transport, infrastructures and water management.

Chapter 6 is about tools specifically conceived for private companies, related specifically to corporate social responsibility, organizational carbon footprint quantification and mitigation actions.

Chapter 7 is the core one, as entails tools related to business continuity, both for private and public organizations. They include asset, business continuity and emergency management and climate change adaptation. In the final sub-chapter, links with the SCMS features are outlined.

Finally, Chapter 8 includes the main conclusions that emerged from the work performed in Task 3.2 and possible future developments.

Annex I lists a glossary of key adaptation terms from the “Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy Reporting Guidelines” and Annex II includes a baseline assessment questionnaire to CRISTAL river pilots.

2. Guidelines objectives and stakeholders addressed

The present guidelines are compiled as part of the activities foreseen in WP3 “Synchro-modal Network Transport Management System” – Task 3.2 “Organizational approach to enhance the Inland Waterways Transport & Logistic (IWT&L) network systems”.

Compared to the core of WP3 tasks, devoted to the implementation of the SCMS, these guidelines can be considered ancillary, as they make individual organizations understand and implement tools that are SCMS prerequisites. They also illustrate organizational and management issues to face challenges such as business continuity, emergency management and climate change adaptation, at an individual organization level.

Synergies and correlations with SCMS are anyway pointed out.

2.1. Objectives

Considering CRISTAL overall objectives, the present guidelines contribute to the following:

1. Create a more sustainable, green, climate-resilient, biodiversity friendly and smart Inland Water Transport and Logistic (IWT&L) infrastructure (chapters 4, 5 and 6)
2. Create a more reliable, competitive and attractive IWT&L system for business (through the new technologies proposed in CRISTAL Project but not only) ensuring the business continuity and climate change adaptation (at the level of individual organizations as well as through the Synchromodal Corridor Management System-SCMS) despite natural or human-caused disruptions (chapter 7)

The guidelines are relevant to some of the WP3 objectives **because they aim at:**

- Limiting transport infrastructure vulnerability to climate change and other natural or human-caused disruptions **addressing individual organizations in the infrastructure with the tools developed in chapter 7**
- Enhancing the resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility and logistics networks [...] operating on the current infrastructure **with the tools developed in sub-chapters 7.2, 7.3 and 7.5, to be implemented by infrastructure managers and transport companies in the network**
- Supporting synchro-modality and optimizing synchromodal flows along the corridors that are linked with IWW **by implementing procedures for data and information sharing**
- Increasing monitoring and the visibility along the transport networks (including emission’s monitoring) **through GHG quantification and reporting at organizations level (sub-chapter 6.2)**
- Strengthening decision making and the cooperation among the different actors involved **by setting procedures for decision-making in different circumstances (sub-chapters 6.1, 7.3 and 7.5)**

Compared with the bulk of the other tasks under the WP3 umbrella, these guidelines are addressed to individual organizations: the actions proposed can be implemented as stand-alone ones or, better, as preliminary steps to be part of and to exploit the advantages offered by SCMS.

According to task 7.3, the guidelines will be implemented at least on a sample of ten private companies and five public bodies in the Italian pilot. They will also be presented to pilots' stakeholders in the framework of the living lab.

The alignment with task and deliverable objectives is reported in sub-chapter 1.2.

2.2. Stakeholders' addressees of the identified guidelines

The present guidelines have been drafted to be as generic as possible and easily applicable to organizations of any type and any size, also considering the actual stage of the project.

Anyway, they are mainly addressed to the following stakeholders:

1. Guidelines to achieve the objective "create a more sustainable, green, climate-resilient, biodiversity friendly and smart Inland Water Transport and Logistic (IWT&L) infrastructure" are relevant to¹:
 - all the stakeholders groups in the transport function: infrastructure managers, transport companies, ports, logistic service providers and shipper and cargo owners
 - linked industries to IWT (farmers' association, power plants, tourism sector)
 - citizens living near the waterway, advocated by their municipalities
2. Guidelines to achieve the objective "create a more reliable, competitive and attractive IWT&L system for business (through the new technologies proposed in CRISTAL Project but not only) ensuring the business continuity and climate change adaptation (at the level of individual organizations as well as through the Synchromodal Corridor Management System-SCMS) despite natural or the human-caused disruptions" are mainly relevant to stakeholders defined as SCMS data and new technologies users.

Other stakeholders (regulators, stakeholders related to other modes of transport) may benefit from some of the features in the present guidelines but they are not specifically addressed.

Information driven from pilots through a questionnaire are reported in **Annex 2**: a further analysis of acquired data is not the aim of this document. Data and information have been collected to give an example and an overview of the current situation about business continuity, emergency management and climate change adaptation in the French, Italian and Polish pilot.

¹ Deliverable 4.1 (Table 2 – sub-chapter 2.5)

3. Drivers leading the sustainable development of IWT L system

The following table shows the regulatory framework at the basis of the idea of the new transport and logistics system that CRISTAL intends to create.

Table 2 Overview of European Legislation on sustainable development and ESG strategy

DRIVERS	Insights
UNO Agenda 2030 – sustainable development goals	<p>United Nations 2030 Agenda set 17 goals for the global sustainable development.</p> <p>The main goals related to CRISTAL project findings are:</p> <p>Goal 9. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation</p> <p>Goal 13. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts</p> <p>Goal 14. Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development²</p>
Green New Deal and 2050 long-term strategy	<p>The EU aims to be climate-neutral by 2050 – an economy with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions. This objective is at the heart of the European Green Deal and in line with the EU’s commitment to global climate action under the Paris Agreement³</p>
EU climate Law (entered into force on 29 July 2021)	<p>This law contains:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal objective for the Union to reach climate neutrality by 2050 • An ambitious 2030 climate target of at least 55% reduction of net emissions of greenhouse gases as compared to 1990, (..)

² <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>

³ climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/climate-strategies-targets/2050-long-term-strategy_en

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognition of the need to enhance the EU's carbon sink through a more ambitious Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) regulation, (..) • A process for setting a 2040 climate target, (..) • A commitment to negative emissions after 2050 • The establishment of European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change, (..) • Stronger provisions on adaptation to climate change • Strong coherence across Union policies with the climate neutrality objective • - A commitment to engage with sectors to prepare sector-specific roadmaps charting the path to climate neutrality in different areas of the economy⁴
<p>EU Climate change adaptation strategy (adopted from 24 Feb 2021)</p>	<p>The new strategy sets out how the European Union can adapt to the unavoidable impacts of climate change and become climate resilient by 2050.</p> <p>The strategy has four main objectives: to make adaptation smarter, swifter and more systemic, and to step up international action on adaptation to climate change.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Smarter adaptation through an EU platform, called Climate-ADAPT, as data and risk assessment tool. 2. Faster adaptation developing and rolling out adaptation solutions to help reduce climate-related risk, increase climate protection and safeguard the availability of fresh water. 3. More systemic adaptation supporting the further development and implementation of adaptation strategies and plans at all levels of governance with three cross-cutting priorities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • integrating adaptation into macro-fiscal policy • nature-based solutions for adaptation • local adaptation action.

⁴ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/european-green-deal/european-climate-law_en

	4 Stepping up international action for climate resilience scaling up of international finance through stronger global engagement and exchanges on adaptation. ⁵
Sustainable finance and Taxonomy	The EU taxonomy would provide companies, investors and policymakers with appropriate definitions for which economic activities can be considered environmentally sustainable. In this way, it should create security for investors, protect private investors from greenwashing, help companies to become more climate-friendly, mitigate market fragmentation and help shift investments where they are most needed. The Taxonomy Regulation establishes six environmental objectives. ⁶ (See Chapter 6 for more details)
Corporate sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)	EU rules require large companies and listed companies to publish regular reports on the social and environmental risks they face, and on how their activities impact people and the environment. (...) This helps investors, civil society organisations, consumers and other stakeholders to evaluate the sustainability performance of companies. ⁷ (See more details in Chapter 6).

⁵ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/adaptation-climate-change/eu-adaptation-strategy_en

⁶ https://finance.ec.europa.eu/sustainable-finance/tools-and-standards/eu-taxonomy-sustainable-activities_en

⁷ https://finance.ec.europa.eu/capital-markets-union-and-financial-markets/company-reporting-and-auditing/company-reporting/corporate-sustainability-reporting_en

4. Management systems standards for individual organizations (public and private entities) as reliability boosters

In this chapter the main features of management systems are listed. They are considered organizational prerequisites for what is requested in the following chapters.

Generally speaking, an organization builds a voluntary management system to understand its processes and make them work toward desired objectives. To perform this, a set of rules and procedures are drawn. Documented information⁸ (information required to be controlled and maintained by an organization and the medium on which it is contained) should report any decision, action or assessment/monitoring activity outcome performed in the context of a management system.

Since they are applicable to a variety of organizations with different sizes, management standards are more about principles, rather than performance and more about processes than products.

Management systems are prepared according to ISO standards: the most known are ISO 9001 (Quality management systems), ISO 14001 (Environmental management systems), and ISO 45001 (Occupational health and safety management systems). Specifically, these three standards have a common “high level structure”, which will be the reference for others management systems, included ISO 22301 – Security and resilience — Business continuity management systems.

This common structure is described in the following table.

Table 3 Common structure of a management system

DRIVERS	Insights
The organization and its context	Defining the context of an organization means understanding/defining: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The organization itself, its processes and its strategic goals - Relevant internal and external factors to their goals - Possible legal or regulatory requirements - The field of application of the management systems (organization departments, activities, products or services) and its boundary

⁸ ISO 9001:2015: Quality management systems — Requirements

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Who are relevant interested parties ⁹ (“person or organization that can affect, be affected by, or perceive itself to be affected by a decision or activity”) and their needs and requirements
Leadership	<p>Leadership is about the commitment of the top management in performing what is in its power, to implement the management system. This implies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Defining the policy and objectives - Ensuring required resources included education/training - Ensuring integration with existing processes - Advocacy and communication of the management system - Checking goals reaching and promoting continuous improvement <p>The commitment is declared in a policy, which is a general reference to set objectives and to define further step. The policy is usually publicly available and communicated to interested parties</p>
Planning	<p>The planning phase is about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Taking into consideration internal and external factors and requisites, assessing risks and opportunities - Designing actions to face them - Establishing how to integrate actions in existing processes and how to monitor their outcomes - Planning is also about setting operational objectives and the management system’s regular updates
Support	<p>The organization commits to provide the resources needed to implement the management system, in terms of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monetary resources and equipment - Skilled staff of training - Spreading awareness about the management system and people with defined roles and responsibilities - Setting communication procedures - Defining rules for documented information

⁹ ISO 9001:2015: Quality management systems — Requirements

5. Supporting tools for public bodies to increase their resilience to natural or human-made disruptive events

The public bodies interested in CRISTAL project activities can be divided in two categories. The first category is made up of the municipalities interested by the vicinity of the inland water way, those that can be compromised by the level of the water in the river. The second category contains the port authorities, the infrastructure operators, the basin authorities and, generally, all the public authorities related to the river regulation in terms of transport, infrastructure, logistic and water utilization.

5.1. Resilience indicators for public authorities and infrastructure operators (e.g., ports)

In this chapter, a list of indicators that can help municipalities to assess their grade of preparedness and readiness, if a disruptive event occurs, will be presented. It means understanding which the gap is to be filled in order to be considered a “resilient city”¹⁰.

“A resilient city is able to prepare for, recover from and adapt to shocks and stresses. Cities are increasingly confronted by shocks, including extreme natural or human-made events which result in loss of life and injury, material, economic, and/or environmental losses and impacts. These shocks can include but are not limited to floods, earthquakes, hurricanes, wildfires, volcanic eruptions, pandemics, chemical spills and explosions, terrorism, power outages, financial crises, cyber-attacks and conflicts. A resilient city is also able to manage and mitigate ongoing human and natural stresses in a city relating to environmental degradation (e.g., poor air and water quality), social inequality (e.g., chronic poverty and housing shortages) and economic instability (e.g., rapid inflation and persistent unemployment) that cause persistent negative impacts in a city.” (ISO 37123:2019 - Sustainable cities and communities - Indicators for resilient cities).

The following indicators have been developed to help cities:

- a) Preparing for/recovering from/adapting to shocks and stresses
- b) Learning from each other by enabling the comparison of a wide range of performance measures and sharing good practices.

Table 4 Groups of indicators analysed in ISO 37123 related to all possible environmental, social and governance risks

INDICATORS

¹⁰ ISO 37123:2019: Sustainable cities and communities — Indicators for resilient cities

1. Economy	8. Housing	15. Transportation
2. Education	9. Population and social conditions	16. Urban/local agriculture and food security
3. Energy	10. Recreation	17. Urban Planning
4. Environment and climate change	11. Safety	18. Wastewater
5. Finance	12. Solid waste	19. Water
6. Governance	13. Sport and culture	20. Reporting and record maintenance
7. Health	14. Telecommunication	

A Resilience assessment for the Municipalities affected by the vicinity to the Inland water ways is mainly focused on flooding and the drought risk scenarios.

For this reason, the indicators that may be more useful to be applied are the followings:

1. Economy

- a. Historical disaster losses as a percentage of city product (*Physical infrastructure - the built structures, systems and assets required for a city's economy to function; Social infrastructure - includes structures that accommodate social services, such as schools, universities, hospitals and prisons; Critical infrastructure - systems, services or assets (physical or virtual) that are vital for the welfare of society*).
- b. Average annual disaster loss as a percentage of city product (*Physical infrastructure, social infrastructure, Critical infrastructure*)

2. Education

- a. Percentage of schools that teach emergency preparedness and disaster risk reduction
- b. Percentage of population trained in emergency preparedness and disaster risk reduction
- c. Percentage of emergency preparedness publications provided in alternative languages
- d. Educational disruption (*number of teaching hours lost annually due to shocks or stresses*)

3. Energy

- a. Number of different electricity sources providing at least 5% of total energy supply capacity
- b. Percentage of critical facilities served by off-grid energy services

4. Environment and climate change

- a. Percentage of natural areas within the city that have undergone ecological evaluation for their protective services
- b. Territory undergoing ecosystem restoration as a percentage of total city area
- c. Annual frequency of extreme rainfall events
- d. Annual frequency of extreme heat events
- e. Annual frequency of extreme cold events
- f. Annual frequency of flood events

5. Finance

- a. Annual expenditure on upgrades and maintenance of city service assets as a percentage of total city budget
- b. Annual expenditure on upgrades and maintenance of storm water infrastructure as a percentage of total city budget
- c. Annual expenditure allocated to ecosystem restoration in the city's territory as a percentage of total city budget
- d. Annual expenditure on emergency management planning as a percentage of total city budget
- e. Total allocation of disaster reserve funds as a percentage of total city budget

6. Governance

- a. Frequency with which disaster-management plans are updated
- b. Percentage of essential city services covered by a documented continuity plan
- c. Percentage of city electronic data with secure and remote back-up storage
- d. Percentage of public meetings dedicated to resilience in the city
- e. Number of intergovernmental agreements dedicated to planning for shocks as percentage of total intergovernmental agreements
- f. Percentage of essential service providers that have a documented business continuity plan

7. Health

- a. Percentage of hospitals equipped with back-up electricity supply
- b. Percentage of population with basic health insurance
- c. Percentage of population that is fully immunized
- d. Number of infectious disease outbreaks per year

8. Housing

- a. Capacity of designated emergency shelters per 100 000 population
- b. Percentage of buildings structurally vulnerable to high-risk hazards

- c. Percentage of residential buildings not in conformity with building codes and standards
- d. Percentage of damaged infrastructure that was “built back better” after a disaster
- e. Annual number of residential properties flooded as a percentage of total residential properties in the city
- f. Percentage of residential properties located in high-risk zones

9. Population and social conditions

- a. Vulnerable population as a percentage of city population (*individuals who have limited capacity to anticipate, cope with, resist and recover from the effects of a disaster*)
- b. Percentage of population enrolled in social assistance programs
- c. Percentage of population at high risk from natural hazards (*number of people in the city at high-risk of exposure to natural hazards*)
- d. Annual percentage of the city population directly affected by natural hazards (*the annual number of people evacuated, relocated, injured or sickened due to natural hazards*)

10. Safety

- a. Percentage of city population covered by multi-hazard early warning system
- b. Percentage of emergency responders who have received disaster response training
- c. Number of hospital beds in the city destroyed or damaged by natural hazards per 100 000 population

11. Solid waste

- a. Number of active and temporary waste management sites available for debris and rubble per square kilometer

12. Telecommunication

- a. Percentage of emergency responders in the city equipped with specialized communication technologies able to operate reliably during a disaster event

13. Transportation

- a. Number of evacuation routes available per 100 000 population

14. Urban/local agriculture and food security

- a. Percentage of city population that can be served by city food reserves for 72 hours in an emergency
- b. Percentage of the city’s population living within one kilometer of a grocery store

15. Urban planning

- a. Pervious land areas and public space and pavement built with porous, draining materials as a percentage of city land area
- b. Percentage of city land area in high-risk zones where risk-reduction measures have been implemented

- c. Percentage of city departments and utility services that conduct risk assessment in their planning and investment
- d. Annual number of critical infrastructures flooded as a percentage of critical infrastructure in the city
- e. Annual expenditure on water retention measures as a percentage of city prevention measures budget

16. Water

- a. Number of different sources providing at least 5 % of total water supply capacity
- b. Percentage of city population that can be supplied with drinking water by alternative methods for 72 hours

The listed indicators might be tested during the future implementation of these guidelines, as foreseen in Task 1.3 of CRISTAL Project.

The above-mentioned indicators, usually applied to municipalities, can be adapted for the assessment of public bodies such as Port Authorities by scaling them to a more restricted area, identifying all the specific activities and the people who work there.

In general, public entities such as ports or other public regulation or infrastructural maintenance entities can be assimilated to the private companies' category as regards the method and tools to evaluate and to increase resilience and will be developed in chapter 6 and 7.

5.2. Covenant of Majors plans (Sustainable Energy and Climate Adaptation Plan - SECAP) for climate change hazards identification and impact on the different municipality sectors

The approach followed in the adaptation pillar of the Covenant of Mayors include:

1. Committing to climate adaptation
2. Conducting a Risk and Vulnerability Assessment (identifying the most relevant climate hazards and most vulnerable sectors)
3. Identifying adaptation goals
4. Defining adaptation actions
5. Monitoring progress

The approach used for conducting a Risk and Vulnerability Assessment (RVA) follows the framework and core concepts of the IPCC AR5 (Figure 2). The risk of climate-related impacts results from the interaction of climate-related hazards (including extreme events and trends) with the vulnerability and exposure (see the definitions in ANNEX I) of human and natural systems. Changes in both the climate system (left side in Figure

2) and socioeconomic processes, including adaptation and mitigation (right side), are drivers of hazards, exposure, and vulnerability.¹¹

Source: IPCC AR5

Figure 1 Illustration of the core concept of risk (AR5), based on IPCC AR5¹²

This approach passes through four steps:

1. The identification of the climate hazards: flooding, drought, storm, extremely hot temperatures, extremely cold temperatures, landslides, biological risk, forest fires, others
2. The hazard analysis: climate territorial data collection, actual hazard assessment, future hazard assessment, level of hazard classification
3. Sectors identification: buildings, transport, energy, water, waste, land use planning, agriculture and forestry, environmental and biodiversity, health, civil protection and emergency, tourism, other (e.g., ICT, Industry, Financial.)
4. Indicators estimation: exposure, sensitivity and adaptive capacity (see the definitions in Annex I)

¹¹ Covenant of Mayors: 2022 assessment- Climate change mitigation and adaptation at local level; Joint Research Centre (JRC) SCIENCE; 2022

¹² Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Part A: Global and Sectoral Aspects. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change; IPCC; VVAA;2014

In this way, a municipality can understand which are the most vulnerable sectors and areas where intervene first with resilient measures, to increase their adaptation grade to climate change events.

6. Supporting tools for private companies to increase their sustainability

Increasing the sustainability of a company means working on three main drivers: Environment, Social and Governance, the ESG logic.

Following the REGULATION (EU) 2020/852 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 18 June 2020, from the environmental point of view, the six Criteria, adopted by EU determining if a particular economic activity aims to reach the sustainability targets are:

1. Actions for climate change mitigation
2. Actions for climate Change adaptation
3. The sustainable usage of hydrological and marine resources
4. Transition to a circular economy and a waste reduction
5. Environmental pollution prevention and control
6. Ecosystems biodiversity and health protection

An economic activity is considered sustainable if it can positively contribute to at least one of the listed objectives and if it does not produce negative impact on the others.

This activity shall also respect the minimum social guarantees for example respect the guidelines OECD for Multinational Corporates and the United Nations principles on companies and human rights.

Moving toward the ESG direction there is also the corporate sustainability reporting directive 2022/2464 called the CSRD directive, that is the implementing tool of the European Green Deal for the sustainable finance.

The CSRD directive states that a company, in its sustainability reporting, should communicate environmental aspects, social and human right factors and governance factors.

As environmental topics:

- mitigation actions to climate change, including greenhouse gas emissions
- adaptation actions to climate change
- water and marine resources preservation
- the use of resources and the circular economy
- pollution control
- biodiversity and ecosystems preservation

As social topics:

- equal treatment and equal opportunities

- working conditions, health and safety
- respect for human rights, fundamental freedoms, democratic standards and principles

As governance topics:

- role of the administrative, management and control bodies of the company
- main characteristics of the company's internal control and risk management systems
- corporate ethics and corporate culture
- customer relationship management and quality control
- advocacy and lobbying activity to policy makers

6.1. Corporate sustainability and accountability on environmental, social and governance issues

An interesting voluntary international standard that a company may follow to analyze its internal structure, its gaps and move towards an ESG logic, is ISO 26000, a Guidance on Social Responsibility (SR).

ISO 26000:2010 defines The Social Responsibility (SR) as¹³ “the responsibility of an organization for the impacts of its decisions and activities on society and the environment through transparent and ethical behavior that:

- Contributes to sustainable development, including the health and welfare of society
- Take into account the expectations of stakeholders
- Is in compliance with applicable law and consistent with international norms of behavior, and
- Is integrated throughout the organization and practiced in its relationships.”

¹⁴ “Sustainable development is about meeting the needs of society while living within the planet’s ecological limits and without jeopardizing the ability of future generations to meet their needs.”

The two main practices for an organization aiming to perceive the social responsibility are to recognize its social responsibility and engage its stakeholders.

The principles of Social Responsibility defined by ISO 26000:2010 are:

¹³ ISO 26000:2010: Guidance on social responsibility

¹⁴ ISO 26000: 2010: Guidance on social responsibility (Clause 2:18; Clause 3.3.5)

1. **Accountability:** an organization should be accountable for its impacts on society, the economy and the environment.
2. **Transparency:** openness about decisions and activities that affect society, the economy and the environment, and willingness to communicate these in a clear, accurate, timely, honest and complete manner.
3. **Ethical behaviour:** an organization should behave ethically, basing its behaviour on the values of honesty, equity and integrity and showing concern for people, animals and the environment and a commitment to address the impact of its activities and decisions on stakeholders' interests.
4. **Respect for stakeholder interests:** an organization should respect, consider and respond to the specific interests of other individuals or groups that comprise the organization's stakeholders.
5. **Respect for the rule of law:** to comply with all applicable laws and regulations, an organization should take steps to be aware of applicable laws and regulations, to inform those within the organization of their obligation to observe and to implement those measures.
6. **Respect for international norms of behaviour:** an organization should respect international norms of behaviour, while adhering to the principle of respect for the rule of law and not become complicit in any negligence, especially in situations or countries where the law or its implementation does not provide for adequate environmental or social safeguards.
7. **Respect for human rights:** an organization should respect human rights and recognize both their importance and their universality, promote them, take steps to respect them and avoid passively accepting or actively participating in the infringement of rights.

Figure 2 Scheme representing a virtuous cycle where each action strengthens the organization and the community to conduct to sustainable development

The Social Responsibility is a non-static process, it evolves with practice.

Analysing deeply how a company should investigate its structure and activities, the ISO 26000 offers a list of seven core-subjects with the relative issues to be take into consideration for each organization.

In particular, the most relevant (for the organization) issues for each core-subject have to be investigated through transversal aspects like economic aspects, health and safety, the value chain, gender balance, communication with stakeholders.

The seven core subjects are:

Figure 3 The seven core-subjects of ISO 26000:2010¹⁵

For every core subject, the organization have to recognize and identify the relevant issues (factors).

Here below the whole list:

¹⁵ ISO 26000 Post Publication Organisation, basic training material

Organizational governance

- Issue 1: Decision-making processes and structure

Human rights

- Issue 1: Due diligence
- Issue 2: Human rights risk situations
- Issue 3: Avoidance of complicity
- Issue 4: Resolving grievances
- Issue 5: Discrimination and vulnerable groups
- Issue 6: Civil and political rights
- Issue 7: Economic, social and cultural rights
- Issue 8: Fundamental principles and rights at work

Labour practices

- Issue 1: Employment and employment relationships
- Issue 2: Conditions of work and social protection
- Issue 3: Social dialogue
- Issue 4: Health and safety at work
- Issue 5: Human development and training in the workplace

The environment

- Issue 1: Prevention of pollution
- Issue 2: Sustainable resource use
- Issue 3: Climate change mitigation and adaptation
- Issue 4: Protection of the environment, biodiversity and restoration of natural habitats

Fair operating practices

- Issue 1: Anti-corruption
- Issue 2: Responsible political involvement
- Issue 3: Fair competition
- Issue 4: Promoting social responsibility in the value chain
- Issue 5: Respect for property rights

Consumer issues

- Issue 1: Fair marketing, factual and unbiased information and fair contractual practices
- Issue 2: Protecting consumers' health and safety
- Issue 3: Sustainable consumption
- Issue 4: Consumer service, support, and complaint and dispute resolution

- Issue 5: Consumer data protection and privacy
- Issue 6: Access to essential services
- Issue 7: Education and awareness

Community involvement and development

- Issue 1: Community involvement
- Issue 2: Education and culture
- Issue 3: Employment creation and skills development
- Issue 4: Technology development and access
- Issue 5: Wealth and income creation
- Issue 6: Health
- Issue 7: Social investment

After this internal assessment, **stakeholders' engagement is fundamental** to address the company's social responsibility. And to build trust and respect.

Create communication channel with stakeholders is a necessity for exchanging knowledge, suggestions, complaints, ideas for solutions and communicate the activities carried on for each core subject. That's why the stakeholders choice become crucial.

These communication channels are not meant to have a marketing or commercial purpose.

The assessment result is setting priorities and short-term and long-term goals.

Monitoring and reviewing is a necessity to improve the Social Responsibility process performance.

6.2. Tools for mitigation actions

According to the IPCC¹⁶, mitigation refers to “human intervention to reduce emissions or enhance the sinks of greenhouse gases” and a mitigation option is “a technology or practice that reduces GHG emissions or enhances sinks”.

In this chapter, the focus is on mitigation options for individual organizations. Downscaling to individual organizations, mitigation measures and plans are usually undertaken on a volunteer basis. Exceptions

¹⁶Annex I: Glossary In: Global Warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change, sustainable development, and efforts to eradicate poverty; VVAA; IPCC; 2018

concern nationally, among European countries, large energy producers and distributors, who are obliged to undertake energy efficiency and an increasing use of renewable energy sources.

Despite not being mandatory, an increasing number of organizations undertakes mitigation initiatives, to improve their environmental footprint, brand visibility and access to finance.

Many standards and GHG programs are available and followed worldwide for organizations to quantify their carbon footprint and inform mitigation actions. Being compliant with these programs or standards brings huge benefits to organizations and their interested parties, such as¹⁷:

1. “Enhances the environmental integrity of GHG quantification
2. enhances the credibility, consistency and transparency of GHG quantification, monitoring, reporting, verification and validation
3. facilitates the development and implementation of GHG management strategies and plans
4. facilitates the development and implementation of mitigation actions through emission reductions or removal enhancements
5. facilitates the ability to track performance and progress in the reduction of GHG emissions and/or increase in GHG removals”

In this deliverable, the mitigation standards used as a reference are those within the family of ISO 14060 and, specifically, ISO 14064-1:2018 “Greenhouse gases - Part 1: Specification with guidance at the organization level for quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions and removals” and ISO 14064-2:2019 “Greenhouse gases - Part 2: Specification with guidance at the project level for quantification, monitoring and reporting of greenhouse gas emission reductions or removal enhancements”.

ISO 14060 family also includes the following standards:

1. ISO 14064-3 details requirements for verifying GHG statements related to GHG inventories, GHG projects, and carbon footprints of products. It describes the process for verification or validation, including verification or validation planning, assessment procedures, and the evaluation of organizational, project and product GHG statements
2. ISO 14065 defines requirements for bodies that validate and verify GHG statements. Its requirements cover impartiality, competence, communication, validation and verification processes, appeals, complaints, and the management system of validation and verification bodies. It can be used as a basis for accreditation and other forms of recognition in relation to the impartiality, competence, and consistency of validation and verification bodies

¹⁷ ISO 14064-1:2018: Greenhouse gases — Part 1: Specification with guidance at the organization level for quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions and removals

3. ISO 14066 specifies competence requirements for validation teams and verification teams. It includes principles and specifies competence requirements based on the tasks that validation teams or verification teams must be able to perform
4. ISO 14067 defines the principles, requirements and guidelines for the quantification of carbon footprint of products. The aim of ISO 14067 is to quantify GHG emissions associated with the life cycle stages of a product, beginning with resource extraction and raw material sourcing and extending through the production, use and end-of-life stages of the product
5. ISO/TR 14069 assists users in the application of ISO 14064-1, providing guidelines and examples for improving transparency in the quantification of emissions and their reporting. It does not provide additional guidance to ISO 14064-1.

The relationship among the said standards is depicted in the following figure:

Figure 4 Relationship among the ISO 14060 family of GHG standards

/Source: ISO 14064-1:2018: Greenhouse gases — Part 1: Specification with guidance at the organization level for quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions and removals/

Specifically, ISO 14064-1 “details principles and requirements for designing, developing, managing and reporting organization-level GHG inventories. It includes requirements for determining GHG emission and removal boundaries, quantifying an organization’s GHG emissions and removals, and identifying specific company actions or activities aimed at improving GHG management [...]”.

Since carbon footprint vocabulary is topic-specific, the standard “terms and definitions”¹⁸ is the reference for the following part of this chapter.

6.2.1. GHG inventory boundaries

The most important preliminary step in GHG accounting is setting organizational and reporting boundaries: this information makes the reader understand what GHG emissions are referred to.

Organizational boundaries have to be defined when a single organization owns different subsidiaries, facilities or offices (installations) in different locations as well as when different organizations carry out activities in the same site.

In these situations, the organization should aggregate GHG emissions and/or removals at the level of any single installation, directly (through monitoring) or indirectly (considering the part it is accountable for, in case of installations shared with other organizations).

Reporting boundaries are important because, on their basis, direct and indirect GHG emissions and/or removals are defined. Direct GHG emissions are defined as “GHG emission from GHG sources owned or controlled by the organization”. For example, they come from a combustion happening within the organization boundaries. The organization boundaries are defined according to the concepts of financial or operational control: the organizational boundary includes any facility or equipment the organization has the power to either operatively control or influence through a financial politic or decision.

Determining indirect emissions is more difficult and significance criteria should be defined, as not-significant emissions can be excluded from the assessment. Significance criteria may be based on emissions volume, the power of the organization of influencing relative sources and sinks, data availability and their accuracy.

GHG inventory categories, according to ISO 14064-1:2018 standards, are:

1. direct GHG emissions and removals
2. Indirect GHG emissions from imported energy
3. Indirect GHG emissions from transport
4. Indirect GHG emissions from the products used by the organization

¹⁸ <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:14064:-1:ed-2:v1:en>

5. Indirect GHG emissions linked to the use of the organization products
6. Indirect GHG emissions from other sources

6.2.2. GHG emissions and removals quantification

At this point the quantification part begins.

First, the organization has to define GHG sources and sinks within the boundary of its organization. Not-relevant ones can be excluded: the criteria used should be declared and explained.

Then, the quantification method is chosen and explained, based on costs and technical feasibility and acceptable levels of uncertainty, accuracy, coherence and reproducibility. The quantification method is used to calculate GHG emissions or removals data, for any source or sink. It can involve direct monitoring or, more often, modelling.

In this second case, the organization should collect relevant data for any source or sink and choose a model for quantification: a model takes data about sources and sinks as input, and gives the associated GHG emissions or removals, as output. It is based on a simplified representation of the physical/chemical processes that make the use of a product or a process cause a GHG emission or removal.

Any GHG amount is converted in ton CO₂e, through appropriate GWPs.

To build a reference against which future emissions/removals have to be compared, a baseline should be defined. A GHG baseline refers to GHG emissions for a relevant year, in the past. If the information listed above are not available for that year, the first monitored year can be assumed as the baseline. An inventory should be built for the reference year.

The baseline year should be periodically revised to make sure it is still representative.

6.2.3. Mitigation activities

Having its baseline, the organization can plan and implement GHG reduction initiatives “[...] to reduce or prevent direct or indirect GHG emissions or enhance direct or indirect GHG removals”.

According to ISO 04064-2:2019 standard, “GHG initiatives on mitigation rely on the quantification, monitoring, reporting and verification of GHG emissions and/or removals”.

Actually, to name GHG projects as such, they should generate GHG emission reductions or removal enhancements, beyond what would have happened without the project. Sources, sinks and reservoirs relevant for the GHG project have to be identified and considered for the baseline definition.

The quantification, monitoring and reporting of GHG emissions and removals, both for the project emissions and the baseline scenario, are based on procedures developed by the project proponent or adopted from a GHG program.

Generally speaking, a GHG project cycle entails:

- A planning phase
- An implementation phase

A GHG reduction project may vary a lot in complexity depending on the project scale and other aspects. An example is given in the following picture.

Figure 4 A typical GHG project cycle¹⁹

If mitigation initiatives are implemented, the organization should quantify and separately assess the GHG reduction initiatives and their associated GHG emissions and removals differences.

Examples of GHG mitigation actions are:

1. Energy efficiency
2. Energy request reduction
3. Technological and process improvement
4. GHG storage and capture
5. Mobility management
6. Alternative fuels and raw materials
7. Reforestation and carbon storage in soil practices
8. Waste minimizing

¹⁹ ISO 14064-2:2019: Greenhouse gases — Part 2: Specification with guidance at the project level for quantification, monitoring and reporting of greenhouse gas emission reductions or removal enhancements

Offset purchasing or development should be accounted separately.

As for mitigation actions, the organization should set mitigation objectives and relevant implementation period, type, interested categories, the linked reduction amount and its unit of measure.

6.2.4. GHG reporting

GHG quantification and mitigation activities can be the subject of a GHG report. It may or may not be independently verified or certified and should be prepared according to its objectives and intended user needs. The GHG report should include information about who is accountable for report drafting, its frequency, structure and format and, moreover, the content to be included.

Among the information to be included in the report, there are the following:

1. The organization description and boundary
2. The baseline year
3. Direct emissions for any GHG in tons CO₂e
4. Indirect emissions for any category in ton CO₂e
5. Baseline year and baseline inventory
6. Quantification approaches
7. GWP and emission/removal coefficients
8. A declaration about the assessment conformity to the standard

7. Tools for Business continuity

Covid-19 pandemic, from which we are still recovering, can be considered the major social disruption event after the second world war. It has hurt companies hardy, of any size and in different fields, all over the world.

Italy, among European countries, has been widely affected with different business sectors (tourism and hospitality industry, non-necessity retail, and other services) prohibited from being open in the first place and restricted at different levels during the following peaks.

According to Statista's report²⁰, in 2020 the Italian market has experienced a negative GDP growth (8,9%) as well as a substantial decrease in industrial production and a shrinkage in consumption volume of many products and services²¹.

The same applied in Europe²² and worldwide²³, although to a different extent depending on countries and business sectors.

Anyway, it is generally acknowledged that organizations are facing or will face in the near future an increasing number of incidents and disruption events, such as cyberattacks, power outages, natural disasters, equipment or infrastructure breakdowns, loss of key workforce, supply chain failures, financial or market threats and social and political instability.

The events just listed, sometimes unpredictable, have the potential to cause harm to businesses and organizations, in terms of time, financial and reputational costs, employee productivity and possible contractual penalties, or even cause their failure.

This is particularly true in an increasing competitive world and for those businesses related to critical services such as logistics and transport services: service continuous availability and reliability and fulfillment of customer's expectations are also stronger key market drivers.

For example, in 2004 the average cost of service downtime worldwide was at USD 42,000 per hour²⁴. A 2014 KPMG survey²⁵ reported that the cost of downtime one year between 2013 and 2014 was estimated

²⁰ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1110978/gdp-growth-forecast-according-to-different-sources-in-italy/>

²¹ <https://escp.eu/news/impact-covid-retailing-italy>

<https://events.debtwire.com/coronavirus-pandemic-european-countries-respond-focus-on-italy>

²² <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/covid-19/economy>

https://copenhageneconomics.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/copenhagen-economics_economic-consequences-covid-19.pdf

²³ <https://sgp.fas.org/crs/row/R46270.pdf>

²⁴ The Definitive Handbook of Business Continuity Management; Vancoppenolle; John Wiley and Sons Ltd.; 2007

²⁵ The 2013-2014 Continuity Insights and KPMG LLP Global Business Continuity Management (BCM) Program

to be over USD 100000 for 36 % of the organization involved, with almost 12 % reporting losses at over USD 1 million.

In this framework, business continuity can be defined as the “capability of an organization to continue the delivery of products and services within acceptable time frames at predefined capacity during a disruption”²⁶. It reflects an organization level of readiness, pursued in a proactive way, to maintain critical functions during and after an emergency or disruption and to recover its full functionality with as little downtime as possible.

Having some type of business continuity planning should be undertaken from all organizations, regardless of revenue, size or industry, even if the degree of commitment may vary depending on these factors. It is fundamental, anyway, for the organizations delivering services for which continuity is a requirement, sometimes legal or contractual. Beyond mandatory requirements, implicit requests such as non-written agreement, common practice and market benchmark, for each product or service, should be considered.

In ISO 22301, “requirements” refers to the group of these different needs and expectations.

Thinking about business continuity helps reduce business and financial costs, fulfill third parties’ expectations, reach organizations’ strategic targets, boost their reputation and accountability and reduce their legal and financial exposure, gaining a competitive advantage over its competitors. In practice, business continuity involves resilience, recovery and contingency. They are defined, according to ISO 22300:2021 standard, as:

- Resilience (preventive): ability to plan and operate adapting to a changing environment
- Recovery (post event): restoration or pre-existing conditions after a disruption and improvement, where appropriate, of operations, facilities, livelihoods or living conditions of affected organizations, based on lessons learnt during the event
- Contingency: possible future event, condition or eventuality. A contingency plan is a last resort when resiliency and recovery plans fail, for example when an unforeseen event occurs. It depicts a strategy/plan for last resort needs.

Business continuity is about a large set of events or disruptions: under this umbrella we can find, for example, business continuity management (sub-chapter 7.2), emergency management (sub-chapter 7.3), recovery plans and disaster recovery (with a specific reference to data and IT systems).

Benchmarking Study; <https://silo.tips/download/the-continuity-insights-and-kpmg-llp-global-business-continuity-management-bcm-p>

²⁶ ISO 22300:2021: Security and resilience — Vocabulary

A complexity assessment can inform the business impact analysis, which is a prerequisite for business continuity, and help understand internal and external interdependencies relevant to critical functions.

In the transport and logistic sector, the Synchronodal Corridor management System (SCMS as defined in D3.1 “Specification on synchronodal transport management system, components and services” and in a following subchapter), its functionalities and some aspects of its architecture comply with some of the requirements of the reference standard for the above-mentioned tools but in an innovative way. SCMS offers the opportunity to optimize capacity, costs and environmental impact through knowledge, data and planning operations sharing and integration. It also allows operations to be partially externalized during a disruption, enabling the chance to find solutions outside the border of an individual organization, in the corridor’s level point. The solutions proposed by the standards are instead often deployed by the impacted organization on its own (with some exceptions). Further details will follow in sub-chapter 7.5.

SCMS can thus be included in the tools to be compliant with international standards about business continuity and emergency management.

From an operational point of view, the first step in business continuity planning is identifying mission-critical assets and services, as a result of a business impact analysis. After that, all sources of possible business disruption must be identified and assessed for their probability and harm to the organization’s operation (risk assessment). Finally, keeping essential functions running at least at a minimum established level during a disaster with a quick recovery is addressed through the implementation of a business recovery plan.

Business continuity management is an iterative process: its plans and procedures should be updated when any relevant change or new information comes up. Its implementation, as well, does not happen just during a disruption, requiring testing and preparedness.

A detailed description of business continuity management systems is entailed in sub-chapter 7.2.

Some of the tools deployed, as a result of business continuity management, include the following:

1. Temporary workarounds, to keep critical functions working until IT applications, systems, facilities, or personnel are again available
2. Use of redundancy of critical resources, spares and data mirroring
3. Back-up (as a service): data back-up means storing data off site or on a remote drive. Although this provides some business continuity, it is not enough since the IT infrastructure and its functioning needs to be recovered as well
4. Cold site: a physical place where employees can work in the event business locations are impacted or not available. A cold site, coupled with data recovery, may help operations to continue
5. Organization preparedness: readiness of alternative sites, business continuity management system well designed, regularly updated and embedded in daily operations

Business continuity procedures usually address the following topics:

1. Communication with customers, vendors and other third parties about a disruption and its consequences on products/services delivered, making sure a pre-determinate level of service is still delivered
2. Business processes restoration order and timing
3. Employees support during an emergency event
4. The required technology to support the business functions and especially for IT processes (disaster recovery)
5. The teams and resources to manage emergency events
6. Ensure staffing levels will be adequate during a disruption
7. Monitoring and report keeping after a disruption event

Business continuity is also about organizations' culture and mindset. In this sense, business continuity management include:

1. Thinking about resilience in designing critical functions and infrastructures, for example maintaining an overcapacity and through staffing rotations.
2. Business continuity education and awareness:
 - Training for employees and dissemination material
 - Cross-department consultation
 - Visits to recovery sites and awareness about available resources in case of a disruption
 - Regular tests and exercises to check if plans meet requirements and will be functional in an actual event
 - Internal and external interdependencies among key functions are taken into consideration (considering the effect of a disruption in the value chain)
 - Involvement of the business continuity manager in key meetings and policy drafting activities
 - Embed business continuity in existing processes
 - Strong commitment from staff as well as from senior management

In the following chapters, details about emergency and business continuity management will be provided, with a focus on the SCMS functionalities that can partially fulfill international standards requirements.

7.1. Asset management

As these guidelines are addressed to stakeholders within IWT&L, this chapter has been drafted because most of these actors own or manage different types of assets. The reference for this sub-chapter is ISO 55000:2014 standard.

According to it, an asset is “an item, thing or entity that has potential or actual value to an organization”. Assets can be both tangible (e.g., infrastructure, buildings, equipment, IT, human resources, etc.) and intangible (e.g., digital assets, patents, legal rights and reputation).

Asset management helps organizations taking the greatest value from their assets and achieve their organizational objectives. It is about the coordinated activities performed on assets, able to return value to

the organization: asset management is thus a balance between costs, opportunities and performance, reputational and business continuity risks.

The fundamentals of asset management are the following:

- Value: asset management is about the value the asset can provide to the organization, not just about the asset itself.
- Alignment: asset management is about putting into practice organizational objectives with technical and financial decisions, plans and activities about assets.
- Leadership: asset management implies the commitment of the top management and, following, of all the levels of an organization.
- Assurance: asset management gives a higher level of confidence that assets will fulfil their required purpose.

ISO describes asset management using a systems approach (graphic from ISO 55000) as shown:

Figure 5 Relationship between key terms

Asset management essentially walks through four phases:

Create/Acquire Asset Phase

The design phase should be the output of a collaboration between design engineers and maintenance reliability professionals: the last ones may point out small changes that may improve asset maintainability.

In this phase, all the information about the asset itself should be collected and made available in easy-to-read format for operators and maintainers.

While considering designing or acquiring new assets, it can also be realized that existing ones are underutilized or are being operated under potential performance levels, opening the door to options different than acquiring new assets.

Utilize/Maintain Phase

Use and maintenance phase are in trade-off: owners tend to push on the utilize phase but with a high risk of unpredicted, high cost and long-lasting maintenance activities.

Instead, predictive maintenance and a balance between operations and maintenance are useful to avoid excessive downtime and to take the most from assets.

Renew Phase

Data about assets should be collected, kept in an accessible format, and used to support optimal renewal or replacement. This must be considered not just when major safety or operational issues arise.

Decision making in organizations is usually not supported by a knowledge of near-real-time condition of assets.

Disposal/Decommissioning Phase

With time and technology progress, many assets become out-of-date and non-competitive. In a life cycle perspective, assets should be maintained/upgraded as much as possible, but this can be done just if data for decision support and a continuous maintenance/improvement program are in place.

A valuable input for a Life Cycle based approach for asset management comes from the European Project AM4INFRA that focuses on cross asset, cross modal and cross border decision making by relevant authorities. As for SCMS, the prerequisites for this goal are “transparency to each other as well as to policy and society, requiring them [relevant authorities] to share a common vision and objectives, in a common language and from a common base of supporting models and data/information structures”.

7.2. Business continuity management

In practice, business continuity means implementing a business continuity management system (BCMS): the system is developed taking into consideration the amount and type of the impact the organization can accept, during and after a disruption. The ultimate aim of a BCMS is thus managing and maintaining processes, capacities and a response team to let the organization survive disruptions and deliver the minimum level of services they have set, even during a disruption.

This chapter is written with reference to the ISO 22301:2019 standard “Security and resilience – Business Continuity management systems – Requirements”.

Business continuity management has been addressed, at the beginning, with the 2012 version of the abovementioned standard, followed by the publication of the ISO 22313:2012 standard “Societal security - Business continuity management systems - Guidance”. In 2015, the two specifications ISO TS 22317 “Societal security - Business continuity management systems - Guidelines for business impact analysis” and ISO TS 22318 “Societal security - Business continuity management systems - Guidelines for supply chain continuity management” have given details about some aspects of BCMS.

Business continuity management has grown as the result of the application of an “all-hazards (“naturally occurring event, human induced event (both intentional and unintentional) and technology caused event with potential impact on an organization, community or society and the environment on which it depends”) approach” when organizations found out they had to face different types of risk, beyond safety ones, in a coherent way.

What follows is an introduction to BCMS, inspired from ISO 22301:2019 standard. BCMS can be considered one of the components of an organization’s general management system, comprising other aspects such as quality (ISO 9001:2015) and environmental impact (ISO 14001:2015). It shares with other management systems the parts described in chapter 4, that are not further discussed here. Similarly, a BCMS is based on the Deming cycle (plan-do-check-act), so that the BCMS is continuously revised based on the monitoring of implemented actions.

7.2.1. Preliminary steps

Understanding the organization needs is the first fundamental step in delivering a BCMS. Relevant third parties’ needs should also be acknowledged, as well as legal and regulatory requirements.

As for internal and external factors in context definition (chapter 4), the most relevant ones in the CRISTAL project framework are:

1. extreme weather events
2. long term climate-related changes
3. other natural processes (sediment transport and deposition)
4. energy/fuel provision
5. infrastructure failure
6. traffic congestion along the waterway
7. waiting time for loading/unloading
8. infrastructure maintenance activities preventing navigation/docking
9. system overload (lack of residual capacity in transport modes, hubs, terminal operations, cargo availability).
10. disruption in ancillary services (IT, administrative, etc.).

Another preliminary important aspect of the organization context is defining the field of application of the BCMS, considering factors, requisites, acceptable risk and organization mission, objectives and obligations: this task implies defining the products and services that should be included in the BCMS and organization departments to be involved.

Finally, an assessment to determine risks and opportunities is run taking into consideration internal and external factors and requirements.

7.2.2. Business impact analysis

The risk assessment, and consequent prioritized activities and business continuity goals, is a result of a business impact analysis (BIA), which should be revisited regularly or in case of significant changes inside or outside the organization.

The BIA contemplates:

1. Defining possible impacts on assets, systems and processes, caused by internal and external factors
2. Setting evaluation criteria, consistent with the organization context (policy, requirements, objectives, field of application)
3. Pointing out activities essential for the delivery of products and services
4. Considering evaluation criteria in point 2 and the possible impacts in point 1, make an estimation of the impact in time caused by an interruption of activities in point 3
5. Define a “maximum tolerable period of disruption” (MTPD) as “the maximum allowable time that the organization’s key products or services is made unavailable or cannot be delivered before its impact is deemed as unacceptable”
6. Set, among all activities at point 3, prioritized activities, as those to be recovered within the MTPD, at least at a “minimum business continuity objective” (MBCO: the minimum level of services and/or products that is acceptable to the organization to achieve its business objectives during an incident, emergency or disaster). For any activity, a recovery time objective (RTO: the minimum level of services and/or products that is acceptable to the organization to achieve its business objectives during an incident, emergency or disaster) helps defining the activities to address first and those which follows and the sequence of actions to be undertaken
7. Define resources needed for prioritized activities
8. Understand relevant dependencies on external factors and interdependencies among prioritized activities.

Once prioritized activities are listed, a risks analysis informs about the likelihood of the events that can impact these activities, and thus on the associated risk. This value has to be compared with a minimum acceptable level of risk, to understand which risks need to be addressed in the following step.

7.2.3. Planning

Once risks to be mitigated has been defined, the organization should think about:

- Actions and an evaluation criteria of their implementation
- Tactical business continuity objective and their practical aspects (what to do, when required resources, who is in charge, how to measure the outcome)

Then, the processes needed to implement actions, with their evaluation criteria, are set.

Among all possible actions, solutions are those which allows prioritized activities to be recovered within their RTO (Recovery Time Objective) at the MBCO (Minimum Business Continuity Objective) and reduce a disruption duration and likelihood and the impact of a disruption on the organization's products and services. Strategies are a group of one or more solutions. A cost analysis may help choose among alternative solutions/strategies.

Flexibility, in terms of adaptability, scalability and subsidiarity, is an important feature of strategies since some aspects or consequences of a disruption may be unknown.

For any strategy the following aspects should be set:

1. Required resources
2. Action accountability
3. Timeline
4. Results evaluation criteria

Strategies are defined for the period before, during and after a disruption.

Finally, a business continuity plan comprises procedures to put strategies into practice when the activation of a business continuity solution is required. It is also about alerting and communicating to interested parties, activating procedures according to relevant predeterminate thresholds, actions to manage ancillary impacts, reporting and a recovery process.

A plan is prepared for any type of relevant disruption event. Collectively, business continuity plans assist response teams and the whole organization in responding and recovering.

In the end, a program set up procedures to maintain, review, audit, test and communicate business continuity plans.

7.3. Emergency and incident management

Compared to business continuity management, emergency management addresses the consequences of an incident from a different perspective. ISO 22320:2018 "Security and resilience – Emergency management – Guidelines for incident management" is the reference for this chapter. The following definitions, taken from ISO 22300:2021 "Security and resilience – Vocabulary", may help in understanding this difference:

- Incident: event that can be, or could lead to, a disruption, loss, emergency or crisis

- Disruption: incident, whether anticipated or unanticipated, that causes an unplanned, negative deviation from the expected delivery of products and services according to an organization's objectives
- Emergency: sudden, urgent, usually unexpected occurrence or event requiring immediate action

Note 1 to entry: An emergency is usually a disruption or condition that can often be anticipated or prepared for, but seldom exactly be foreseen.

Thus, business continuity, which addresses disruptions, is focused on business operations: it aims at maintaining them at least at a minimum accepted level, even during an incident (sub-chapter 7.2 **Error! Reference source not found.**).

Emergency management has actually a different purpose because it is about:

- People (organization's personnel or the public) health and safety and environmental protection (e.g., avoiding or containing spills)
- Reduce harm and damage in a broad sense (within the organization or outside)
- Ensuring the delivery of essential collective functions (health, communication, water and food supply, access to energy, just to mention some)

From the definitions above, an emergency is different from a disruption because:

- A disruption, against an emergency, may not have implications for human health and safety and for the environment (e.g., an infrastructure or equipment failure)
- An incident causing an emergency can occur outside the borders of an organization, even if its impacts affect the organization
- An incident timing an evolution as well as some aspects of its nature and consequences are unpredictable

As a consequence of the last point, compared to business continuity management, incident management:

- Requires some planning activity to be carried out during the event
- Requires resources not readily available and sometimes not within the organization power
- Can be led by different organizations and/or public bodies (fire department, civil protection)

Therefore, and considering emergency usually has a larger impact than a disruption, incident management requires a greater cooperation with external organizations and/or government agencies, compared with business continuity management: this implies being able to effectively communicate with them as well as with other interested parties, the public included.

For larger events, cross-organization/region or border assistance may be appropriate. As for CRISTAL, this is appropriate for waterways crossing different countries. Incident management also applies to events with different time scales, from short-term to long-term events.

Interestingly, within the scope of ISO 22320:2018, we can find the specification that [the standard] "is applicable to any organization with one organizational structure as well as for two or more organizations

that choose to work together while continuing to use their owned organizational structure or to use combined organizational structure”.

A fundamental prerequisite to reach this goal is sharing a common approach/direction (multi-organizational or even multi-national) to incident management. This enables collaborative work, carrying out complementary actions among organizations, sharing recovery burden leading to cost reduction and increased efficiency.

Similar to business continuity, incident management concerns facilities, equipment, personnel, organizational structure, procedures and communication. It comprises:

- Incident management process (planning included)
- Incident management structure

In the following sub chapters, these two aspects are outlined.

7.3.1. Incident management process

Incident management process starts with gathering external information about the incident, internal data resulting from monitoring, data processing (and sharing) to assess the situation and to estimate its time path.

The following step is setting incident management objectives and, accordingly, agree about decision-making (the criteria used to make decisions and to choose among alternatives) and communication procedures. An incident action plan, with aspects about the management of the relationships with other organizations, is then developed and communicated.

Acknowledged the nature of incidents described above, in developing an incident management plan is important to take into consideration different perspectives and needs and to assess alternative options for acting.

Finally, the plan should be implemented: acting timely is important to avoid cascading effect. Being proactive is also valuable, to make sure decisions are taken early enough to be implemented in time to deliver the desired effect. An agreement about who should take decisions and initiate action is useful: if this lacks, it is better to initiate a joint response rather than waiting.

7.3.2. Incident management structure

Incident management structure enables the incident management process to be put into practice, carrying out the tasks defined in the incident management plan.

An incident management structure includes:

- Definition of roles and responsibilities for the measures to be implemented, defining thus the organizational structure and the power/control chain. A person in charge of the overall command, with the authority to give orders, release resources and supervise communication activities, should be appointed. The organizational structure should be compliant with the principle of the unity of command (any person at any time reports only to one supervisor)
- Planning: since events are sudden, their nature and extent somehow unpredictable, planning cannot be performed entirely before the event. The organization should also be able to take into consideration changes in circumstances and adjust decisions, if necessary
- Operations: actions implementation, status and monitoring results reports, gathering and sharing information and transition to the recovery phase
- Logistics: allocation of different types of resources needed to support people and the execution of an incident management plan: facilities, supplies, equipment, IT and communication technologies, transport services, provisioning for basic personnel needs
- Administrative and financial functions (just for larger events): procurement, management of costs assuring, financial support seeking, insurance reporting

As already said, coordination and cooperation are fundamental for large-scale events. Cooperation is about working together among the same organization and within different organizations.

The most important prerequisite for cooperation is an agreement on incident objectives, that results in operating with a common direction. To do that, it is mandatory to build the whole picture, going beyond single organizations scope of operations and being aware of the other organizations involved and their capability.

Then, an agreement should be reached on how to address the incident, through sharing the same incident management process. A clear and transparent decision-making process is also fundamental for others to understand how an organization works and be confident about decisions made.

If the public is involved and communication about the incident is required, protocols for coordinated communications should be established to booster credibility and prevent misunderstanding. Communicate timely and in an understandable way for the recipient is important as well.

7.4. Climate change adaptation and its planning

Climate change adaptation can be considered as a subset of business continuity management, when disruptions are climate-change related.

A huge literature body about climate change adaptation is available at different scales, from international to local: what follows comes from ISO 14090:2019 “Adaptation to climate change – Principles, requirements

and guidelines” and ISO 14091:2021 “Adaptation to climate change - Guidelines on vulnerability, impacts and risk assessment” standards and from PIANC report n. 78²⁷.

Since climate change future scenarios are uncertain, as they partially are related to emissions patterns, not yet known, and forecasting models cannot exactly simulate natural processes, climate change adaptation incorporates an even higher level of uncertainty than business continuity management. Climate change has effects on many different features of a business and its value chain both in the short and long term, as well.

Therefore, flexibility, robustness (the target is met in a wide range of different climate conditions), subsidiarity, sustainability (economic, social and environmental aspects and present and future generation needs being considered equally), a change-oriented perspective (solutions may be different from conventional ones) and system thinking (understanding internal and external interdependencies and thus cross-cutting or systemic issues) are essential. Indeed, when it comes to climate change, overlooking interdependencies may lead to underestimated impacts.

Finally, acknowledged that climate change is already ongoing and will keep happening in the future, it should be considered that fighting climate change is both about mitigation and adaptation: mitigation measures (sub-chapter 6.2) should thus be taken together with adaptation ones.

7.4.1. Pre-planning

Pre-planning is about making sure the organization has the capability to undertake the following steps. Pre-planning is performed by:

- Ensuring people with the right level of knowledge and expertise are engaged
- Determining roles and responsibilities for the whole staff involved
- Appointing a person in charge of the leadership and ownership of the process
- Supplying financial and other type of resources needed
- Assessing if relevant data and information are accessible

In this preliminary stage, a consultation with relevant stakeholders or third parties (suppliers, vendors, customers, shareholders and government/regulatory authorities) may bring further elements to build up the big picture, share vision, objectives and commitment for actions to be implemented along the adaptation pathway.

²⁷ Climate change adaptation planning for ports and inland waterways; EnviCom WG Report n. 178; PIANC; 2020

In this phase, relevant data are collected: data to inform climate change adaptation are preferably local and, above all, fit-for-purpose. Record keeping about extreme events consequences and frequency is also valuable.

The main types of data to be gathered are on:

- Operational efficiency and performance of physical assets
- Extreme events costs and consequences, downtime included, to estimate cost of inaction
- Local meteorological and hydrological data, to understand local trends and inform about threshold approaching (sub-chapter 7.4.5)
- In case some adaptation measures have already been implemented, their effects.

Having collected data is of course not enough: a robust, effective, secure and on-time data management system should be put in place.

A final important task in pre-planning is identifying critical assets, operations and systems (AOS). They are determined applying the following procedure:

- Preparation of an inventory of infrastructure assets (e.g., port and waterway assets, hinterland assets linked with port or waterway operations), operations (maintenance dredging, vessel services, passage planning, cargo handling, pilotage) and supporting (IT) systems (RIS, vessel traffic systems, tracking systems, port security and administrative services)
- Depicting external interdependencies for port/waterway functions: connecting road or rail infrastructure, energy and water supply, wastewater treatment, supply chain terminals, distribution and storage centers
- Figuring out AOS criticality: “critical infrastructure refers to assets or systems and associated operations that are of relatively greater importance because their disruption or destruction would have a significant adverse impact on the continued functioning of the port or waterway, or they are indispensable in some other way”. Criticality can be assessed, as a first option, in a qualitative way.

The concept of critical AOS is comparable with “mission-critical assets and services” in sub-chapter 7.2. In this sense, determining criticality is not climate-change specific because it refers to the potential consequences of an asset, operation or system compromise for a period of time.

Criticality assessment is usually based on local expertise and should be extended to relevant third-party activities or services.

7.4.2. Susceptibility assessment

This is the core stage of climate change adaptation, to develop a tailored plan that actually addresses the critical aspects for any individual organization.

It explains how and why an organization AOS might be impacted by climate change. This complex task implies initially an assessment of assets, operations and systems susceptibility: it indicates “whether an

asset, operation or system is prone to harm, to disruption or to other adverse effects as a result of changes in meteorological [...] or hydrological characteristics”. It is thus a way to understand if an asset, operation or system is exposed or not to a risk and how much it is prone to harm if a hazard arises.

Compared to the methodology used in SECAP, susceptibility encompasses both exposure and sensitivity (sub-chapter 5.2). Vulnerability (sub-chapter 7.4.5) incorporates susceptibility and adaptive capacity.

This exercise should be performed for any combination critical AOS/climate-related hazard.

Examples of the most relevant hazards for inland navigation²⁸ are:

- Flooding due to overwhelmed drainage systems or high groundwater levels
- Overtopping and flooding due to high river flow levels
- High in channel river flow velocities
- Changes in bathymetry, in sediment or debris transport, deposition and accumulation
- Riverbed erosion
- Fog or other reduced visibility
- Extreme cold, ice or icing
- Extreme heat and/or humidity
- Changes in water chemistry
- Changes in biological aspects (vegetation growth rates, species migration, invasive species)

Assessing susceptibility is preferably informed by reports on past adverse effects and their consequences but can also be performed as a theoretical exercise. In the second option, local knowledge and the expert judgment of accountable people must be valued as much as possible. Information about design data and current conditions should also be considered.

If information is insufficient or too vague, a monitoring system/record keeping can be put in place: to be effective, the monitoring system should be targeted and developed considering the scale of the facility and the required data quality. A monitoring system is also worthwhile for the following steps in adaptation planning as it let improve preparedness and inform decisions on how and when initiate action, especially if a threshold approach to adaptation (sub-chapter 7.4.5) is undertaken.

²⁸ Climate change adaptation planning for ports and inland waterways; EnviCom WG Report n. 178; PIANC; 2020

7.4.3. Setting objectives

Before actual adaptation planning is initiated, adaptation objectives are set. Practically, adaptation objectives are often a function of very down-to-earth factors such as data, budget and resources availability, environmental, financial, regulatory and policy constraints, action ownership and legal limitations.

Climate change adaptation arises the chance to seek opportunities, at the same time. Collaboration within the organization and with stakeholders might link adaptation measures with corporate social responsibility programs, share services, deliver co-benefits (social, recreational, socio-economic or environmental), especially if nature-based solutions are implemented.

In this sense, SCMS enables value creation by sharing information and services and boosting reliability and sustainability of IWT&L.

The planning horizon strongly influences objectives, also because of the uncertainty related with scenarios far in the future. As a consequence, knowing the planning horizon is critical both to set objective and to understand the type of data needed and the nature of the analysis required. Usually, an adaptation strategy covers a period of time comparable with assets lifetime.

In theory, objectives should be specific, measurable, attainable, realistic and timely (SMART). In practice, this depends on the information and the level of knowledge and expertise available.

As already said in the introduction of chapter 7, given the uncertainty of long-term climate scenarios, a flexible approach should be taken for determining objectives, as well.

7.4.4. Collecting climate information

Climate data should be collected both to understand slow onset changes (related to chronic impacts) and to forecast changes in frequency and magnitude of extreme meteorological and hydrological events (related to acute impacts).

Forecasts gain a value just if compared with baseline conditions and with the inclusion of data limitations and uncertainty in the assessment.

Generally speaking, data are available at different spatial and temporal scales and with different levels of details: a decision should be made about appropriate data to collect, considering the scope of the adaptation plan, its time horizon, resources available and the hazards to which critical assets, operations and systems are susceptible.

Examples of climate (related) parameters or processes linked to the hazards listed before:

- Air temperature
- Water temperature

- Precipitation
- Storminess
- Water level

A baseline is built on historical observed, measured or modelled data: it is the reference against which possible implications of future climate change are defined. Setting baseline conditions is also useful to understand existing patterns or trends and their ongoing impacts on critical AOS.

Apart from local data, there are a number of sources of publicly available data. Extreme events should be included in baseline definition.

Assessing possible future climate conditions is an exercise which depends strongly on the planning horizon: if for short-term plans taking into consideration current trends may be enough, for >10 years-long plans, projections are needed. In this case, uncertainty increases and different scenarios should be considered. A reference, in this case, are the “representative concentration pathways” (RCPs) with linked mean temperature global increase. RCPs reflect greenhouse gas concentration trajectories developed by IPCC²⁹, based on the different level of effort undertaken to fight climate change.

The longer the adaptation strategy, the highest the number of scenarios to be considered, as they diverge a lot with time. Seldom, a model simulation is performed for this task, because of the availability of public data. Anyway, conventional statistical methods based on return periods should be used with care to reliably predict the frequency of low-probability future events, even if long-term datasets are available: the conditions enabling an event now may not happen in the same way in the future (especially if tipping points are reached). In this case, the consequences of a “unlikely-but-plausible” future event, assessed pragmatically are fundamental to avoid maladaptation “failing to adjust adequately or appropriately or appropriately to an anticipated change [...]”.

7.4.5. Vulnerability assessment and risk analysis

At this point, information about critical AOS and forecasted data about climate-related parameters, linked to hazards to which AOS are susceptible, are put together to work out a vulnerability assessment and eventually a risk analysis.

A vulnerability assessment describes how climate hazards (due to projected changes in climate parameters) are compared to the baseline situation to highlight changes in the vulnerability (“the degree to which a system is susceptible to, and unable to cope with, adverse climate change effects, including climate

²⁹ Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change; Cambridge University Press; VVAA; IPCC; 2013

variability and extremes. Vulnerability is a function of the character, magnitude and rate of climate change and variation to which an asset, operation or system is exposed, its sensitivity [...] and its adaptive capacity”) of critical AOS. Adaptive capacity means “having the ability to adjust to change”.

Vulnerability is AOS specific, as it depends on its susceptibility, proximity to relevant thresholds (see forward) and adaptive capacity.

A vulnerability assessment can stand alone or be a preliminary process for a risk analysis. For any AOS, a vulnerability assessment fundamentally answers the question: can a projected change in a relevant climate parameter or process, against the current situation, or a new climate hazard lead to an impact to the AOS? If yes, is there sufficient adaptive capacity? An impact is linked to a change in susceptibility that imply the exceedance of a functioning threshold or cause another type of damage or disruption.

There is a broad range in complexity in vulnerability assessments, from qualitative ones to quantitative modelling.

In vulnerability assessment for climate change adaptation, a threshold-based approach is usually undertaken because a small change in a climate parameter cannot result in a significant impact. Thresholds, thus, capture the point at which a change in climate-related parameter or process might be expected to cause damage, compromise the integrity of an asset or lead to an operational disruption. It should be considered that this approach is relevant just for climate-related parameters as other types of factors, e.g., safety-related ones, lead an impact at any level of occurrence.

These thresholds usually match design and operational thresholds, that are set for an acceptable level of risk for the corresponding AOS. Sometimes, a residual or acceptable risk, higher than that corresponding to a threshold, is accepted, depending on boundaries, constraints and availability of resources.

A threshold-based approach provides a consistent and practical information: exceeding a threshold means an impact is likely.

Before concluding about vulnerability assessment, it is important to explore the role of adaptive capacity: usually, critical AOS has some level of adaptive capacity incorporated. Adaptive capacity can consist in redundancy, over-designing, back-ups and resources foreseen in emergency plans.

The final output is again an assessment of vulnerability for any possible combination of AOS/climate hazard.

The last potential step to convert a vulnerability assessment in a risk one, considers the likelihood and the potential consequences of a threshold being exceeded/a defined increase in a climate parameter. Further details on this topic go beyond the scope of this document. Uncertainty should also be accommodated. The output points out, among others, impacts at high risk. This information is useful to set priorities for the following step.

7.4.6. Adaptation options, measures and plans

The final and most important step in climate change adaptation is identifying, screening and, if appropriate, rating possible adaptation and resilience options. Options comprise measures or group of measures to deal with identified risks. An adaptation pathway is made of a series of actions, to be implemented in response to changes in meteorological or hydrographic conditions, for each AOS. Finally, an adaptation strategy is prepared: its performance against the objectives is informed by monitoring; adjustments in adaptation pathways may follow.

The first step is designing single measures, to make up a portfolio. Figuring out adaptation measures can be a challenging task because they usually consistently deviate from business-as-usual. Actually, the need to accommodate a high degree of uncertainty means that conventional solutions may not be the best ones. This implies developing a long-term vision and thinking out-of-the-box.

As a consequence, there is a high risk of maladaptation (“failing to adjust adequately to an anticipated event [...]. An asset could ultimately be over-designed or under-designed and (some of) the initial investment may be wasted. [...]. Interventions that increase vulnerability at another location or of another sector are also considered as maladaptation”).

Maladaptation usually comes from not having considered the whole picture, interdependencies and the consequences of simultaneous events. If necessary, short-term measures can help strengthen resilience right away to gain time to collect data to address uncertainty for long-term measures.

Thinking outside the box in designing means accommodating uncertainty, with a flexible and modular design, keeping in mind that the need for future modifications may imply an asset retrofitting or replacing incorporating flexibility in design helps accommodate future infrastructure upgrading or modifications. For equipment, redundancy may be appropriate. Finally, where structures or operations are prone to failure, understanding the consequences may be vital: design of an infrastructure and its context should allow not to fail catastrophically, by thinking about what happens when an infrastructure fails. Indeed, accepting and accommodating higher levels or fast changing risks implies it will be impossible to provide protection against all possible risks.

Understanding when to act is another important issue: rather than having a plan fixed in time, it is better to implement adaptation actions when a specific threshold is exceeded, thus enabling decisions about implementation being informed by monitoring in a stepwise mode.

Sometimes, a single solution may be enough in terms of residual risk. Usually, however, an adaptation pathway comprising a group of measures is preferable, starting with temporary or interim actions, that immediately partially reduce risks, whilst data are gathered and confidence improves to identify the most

suitable longer-term options. Adaptation measures are usually referred to infrastructure ones, but IPCC³⁰ classifies measures in

- Physical: structural, engineered, technological systems as well as soft engineering measures, such as nature-based solutions
- Social: operational, management, educational, information-related and behavioral measures
- Institutional: governance, economics, law, regulation, policies and programs.

A screening of measures portfolio is done to figure out the most simple and cheap ones, those which bring synergic benefits if combined, no or low-regret measures (“solutions that provide benefits under any foreseeable climate scenario including present day climate [...]”, win-win measures (providing co-benefits to other stakeholders).

Measures selected are finally screened against locally applicable criteria, are directly related to the objectives. Weighing factors may also be applied.

Examples of screening criteria include³¹:

- Compatible with objectives
- Relative cost
- Technical feasibility
- Level of risk reduction
- Implications for other users or stakeholders
- Impacts on physical or natural environment or heritage assets
- Maintenance or management requirements
- Risk of maladaptation
- Extent of co-benefits
- Represents a no or low-regret measures

The screening can be qualitative or quantitative.

Shortlisted options may undertake a more detailed analysis (cost-benefit analysis, cost effectiveness analysis, multi-criteria analysis or six-capitals assessment³²).

As already said, since climate adaptation incorporates a high degree of uncertainty, planning for climate adaptation means defining a pathway rather than a plan or program: it is difficult or impossible to know

³⁰ Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change; Cambridge University Press; VVAA; IPCC; 2013

³¹ Climate change adaptation planning for ports and inland waterways; EnviCom WG Report n. 178; PIANC; 2020

³² <https://www.integratedreporting.org/what-the-tool-for-better-reporting/get-to-grips-with-the-six-capitals/>

exactly when a particular intervention may need to be triggered or a new measure to be introduced. To avoid maladaptation, this flexibility in implementation is crucial.

Thus, there will not be a fixed data for measures implementation: usually, cheaper and simpler measure are within the first step on the adaptation pathway. They can be implemented with confidence waiting for monitoring outcomes to inform long-term interventions.

If choices have to be made about measures to implement, because of budget, legal or other type of constraint, the organization should have an internal process to set priorities.

The strategy contains measures to be implemented according to the adaptation pathway for each AOS, the priorities for their implementation, roles and responsibilities, especially if stakeholders are involved, but also an extract of the background and of the process that led to the decisions undertaken.

Finally, the adaptation strategy should be communicated and shared with relevant third parties and to be accommodated according to their inputs.

7.4.7. Implementation

The implementation of measures can be simple, e.g., for behavioral changes, or complex, e.g., for structural measures with many interrelated elements. These second measure request significant planning and preparation, considerable resources and more years to be implemented.

Implementation usually comprises:

- Set up a project team(s)
- Define leadership and commitment
- Engage third parties or influencing stakeholders
- Educate and build capacity or engage external resources with required knowledge or expertise
- Preparation, planning and designed, if not already performed
- Launching, implementation and process documentation
- Adjustment providing, if needed
- Monitoring and reviewing (during execution)

Finally, a monitoring plan of implemented measures can both inform future actions on the adaptation pathway and avoid maladaptation. Monitoring involve quantification, as far as possible, and be aligned with objectives.

7.5. Sychromodal corridor management system

In Deliverable 3.1 SCMS preliminary features and functionalities have been described. SCMS is one of the most important systems developed in CRISTAL, specifically in WP3, as it enables sychromodal corridor management, which is “the process of integrating the corridor of the three different modes aiming at orchestrating transport flow in a manner that ensures the efficient utilization of the network and deals with

planned and unplanned disruption. Synchronodal corridors are also referred as green transport corridors, due to their environmental impact³³.

For further details about the SCMS developed in CRISTAL, see Deliverable 3.1.

As for the present document, the aim is to highlight those SCMS functionalities that meet the requirements for business continuity management and planning under uncertainty as described in the previous chapters, for the individual organizations/stakeholders that are involved in the river corridor transport network. The reference used for this purpose is D3.1 (Table 8, and the list of objectives reported in section “Description of the main goals and objectives of the system” as summarized in Table 9). They are reported here to ease reading. For each SCMS functionality, the way it can contribute to the requirements of the tools described in the previous chapters are highlighted in Table 4, while Table 5 relates SCMS goals and objectives to BCM. It should be noted though, that the SCMS functionalities and objectives listed below represent a system in its full development and implementation. The development of some SCMS functionalities depends on various factors, such as the access to data and information, the ability to switch between transportation modes along the corridor in short term, the commitment to optimal utilization of corridor resources and the level of collaboration among stakeholders. However, regardless of the level of SCMS development, and specifically within the scope of CRISTAL project, synchronodality may assist to business continuity, as highlighted in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 5 Contribution of synchronodality to BCM

Synchronodality Characteristics/Requirements	Possible influence on SCMS	Contribution to BCM
Real-time switching between transportation modes	Dynamic switching between modes based on real-time traffic, network conditions, and other relevant factors	Maximizing efficiency and vehicles utilization under uncertainty helps reducing GHG emissions and maintain systems resilience and quality of services
Optimal utilization of multimodal transport network resources	Optimize utilization of resources, including transport vehicles and infrastructure, to minimize costs and maximize efficiency	Maximizing efficiency and vehicles utilization helps reducing GHG emissions linked to the overall service

³³ Deliverable 3.1, sub-chapter 2.3

Cooperation between transport actors	Facilitate cooperation between transport actors, such as shippers, carriers, logistics service providers, and infrastructure operators, for seamless and coordinated transportation operations	Coordination and cooperation among the same organization and within different organizations are fundamental aspect for dealing with disruptions and incidents
Real-time optimization and network service design	Continuously monitor and optimize transportation operations in real-time, using data and information from the network	Monitoring reduced cost through a shared service. Also, a monitoring system is necessary for adaptation planning as it increases preparedness and inform decisions on how and when to initiate actions
Tactical and operational decisions influenced by planning horizon	Use planning horizon to make tactical and operational decisions that balance short-term and long-term goals and priorities	Can inform the decision-making process both for emergency management and climate adaptation
Dynamic transportation planning	Quickly and effectively plan for unforeseen shipments, using real-time data and network information	Real-time rerouting secures the on-time fulfilment of transport services in the proper quality, ensuring the business continuity
Capacitated transport network	Model optimal distribution of capacity between different transportation modes and vehicles	Transport optimization based on capacity utilisation assists in GHG emissions reduction and enhances transport network's resiliency
Multi-commodity and multi-stakeholder	Take into consideration the needs and requirements of multiple commodities and multiple stakeholders	It makes share the effort of understanding stakeholder needs and engaging them. Cooperation is at the core of BCM
Real-time network information, transparency, and data exchange	Use real-time network information and data exchange to improve decision-making and	Real time data and sharing information through horizontal and vertical integration can

	optimize transportation operations	inform decisions about business continuity in case of disruptions
--	------------------------------------	---

To summarize, as described in D3.1, the SCMS is a unified system that introduces the exchange of standardized real-time messages to effectively predict natural or man-made corridor disruptions in order to effectively support uninterrupted operation in given transport networks, increasing the resilience of the entire transport system. The cornerstone of SCMS is the real-time decision making supported by close cooperation and synergies among the stakeholders (data availability, information sharing etc.). On the other hand, the ultimate aim of a BCMS is managing and maintaining processes, capacities and a response team to let the organization survive disruptions and deliver the minimum level of services they have set, even during a disruption (resilience, recovery and contingency). SCMS therefore (network oriented), may serve as a primary tool to support BCM (organization oriented) and vice versa, while at the same time embracing principals and guidelines developed for BCM in the IWT actors.

8. Conclusions

The main purpose of this deliverable is providing a framework for individual organizations to develop the CRISTAL project innovations, either technological or digital: the first ones aim at improving navigability in IWW while the second ones refer to management platforms (i.e., SCMS) to establish an IWT & L system more reliable and resilient to climate change and human-made disruptive events.

An overview of the international and European legislation on sustainable development, ESG requirements for companies and climate change resilience and adaptation for public bodies and communities has been conducted.

After that, the focus has shifted to the analysis of specific tools to make organizations more reliable, well-structured and able to face the occurrence of natural or human-based disruptive events.

The principal tools highlighted has come from ISO standards and are related to resilience and adaptation to climate change (i.e., ISO 37123 Sustainable cities and communities – indicators for resilient cities, ISO 14090 Adaptation to Climate Change principles – requirements and guidelines, ISO 14091 Adaptation to Climate Change – guidelines on vulnerability impacts and risk assessment) and business continuity (i.e., ISO 22301 – Security and resilience – Business continuity management systems). The link with SCMS features has been pointed out.

The organizational prerequisites for the implementation of the proposed tools are common and are taken from the first part of management standards high level structure (e.i. ISO 9001-Quality management systems, ISO 14001 -Environmental management systems and ISO 45001- Occupational health and safety management systems).

The main challenge was to adapt and fit standards to the CRISTAL project topic and stakeholders.

A questionnaire was sent to the infrastructure managers of CRISTAL River pilots (VNF in France, Infrastrutture Venete and AIPO in Italy and Wody Polskie in Poland), to assess their awareness and current practices related to the topics addressed in the guidelines.

The initial situation appears different among the three river pilots: while drought, flood and structure failures are considered a disruption for all the infrastructure managers, just the French one has been able to monetize the impact of past disruptions. All of them manage critical assets but just the French pilot carries out a risk analysis on a regular basis; the Italian pilot has assessed the risk in a qualitative way while the Polish one has been unable to provide this information. The French and Polish pilot and AIPO have datasets to estimate natural disruptions likelihood. Even if all the pilots have some monitoring activities in place, just the French one is carrying out different activities related to business continuity and emergency management. To better fit our guidelines to CRISTAL goals and topics, the project foresees their implementation and testing on at least ten companies and 5 public bodies in the Italian pilot.

9. References

- [1] ISO 9001:2015 Quality management systems — Requirements
- [2] ISO 14001:2015 Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use
- [3] ISO 14064-1:2018 Greenhouse gases — Part 1: Specification with guidance at the organization level for quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions and removals
- [4] ISO 14064-2:2019 Greenhouse gases — Part 2: Specification with guidance at the project level for quantification, monitoring and reporting of greenhouse gas emission reductions or removal enhancements
- [5] ISO 14064-3:2019 Greenhouse gases — Part 3: Specification with guidance for the verification and validation of greenhouse gas statements
- [6] ISO 14090:2019 Adaptation to climate change — Principles, requirements and guidelines
- [7] ISO 14091:2021 Adaptation to climate change — Guidelines on vulnerability, impacts and risk assessment
- [8] ISO 22301:2019 Security and resilience — Business continuity management systems — Requirements
- [9] ISO 26000:2010: Guidance on social responsibility
- [10] ISO 55001:2014 Asset management — Management systems — Requirements
- [11] ISO 22320:2018 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Guidelines for incident management
- [12] ISO/TS 22375:2018 Security and resilience — Guidelines for complexity assessment process
- [13] ISO 37123 Sustainable cities and communities – indicators for resilient cities
- [14] ISO 50001:2018 Energy management systems — Requirements with guidance for use
- [15] Covenant of Mayors: 2022 assessment- Climate change mitigation and adaptation at local level; Joint Research Centre (JRC) SCIENCE; 2022
- [16] Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change; Cambridge University Press; VVAA; IPCC; 2013
- [17] Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Part A: Global and Sectoral Aspects. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change; IPCC; VVAA; 2014
- [18] Annex I: Glossary In: Global Warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change, sustainable development, and efforts to eradicate poverty; VVAA; IPCC; 2018
- [19] The Definitive Handbook of Business Continuity Management; Vancoppenolle; John Wiley and Sons Ltd.; 2007
- [20] Climate change adaptation planning for ports and inland waterways; EnviCom WG Report n. 178; PIANC; 2020

10. Appendices

Annex I - Glossary of key adaptation terms³⁴

Key Adaptation Terms

Adaptation	Adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli or their effects, which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities. Various types of adaptation can be distinguished, including anticipatory, autonomous and planned adaptation.
Hazard	The potential occurrence of a natural or human-induced physical event or trend or physical impact that may cause loss of life, injury, or other health impacts, as well as damage and loss to property, infrastructure, livelihoods, service provision, ecosystems, and environmental resources. In this template, the term hazard usually refers to climate-related physical events or trends or their physical impacts.
Exposure	The presence of people, livelihoods, species or ecosystems, environmental functions, services, and resources, infrastructure, or economic, social, or cultural assets present in hazard zones that are thereby subject to potential losses.
Sensitivity	Sensitivity is the degree to which a system is affected, either adversely or beneficially, by climate variability or change.
Vulnerability	Degree to which a system is susceptible to, and unable to cope with, adverse effects of climate change, including climate variability and extremes.
Impact	Impacts generally refer to potential effects (without adaptation) on lives, livelihoods, health, ecosystems, economies, societies, cultures, services, and infrastructure due to the interaction of climate change or hazardous climate events occurring within a specific time period. Impacts are also referred to as consequences.
Risk	The potential for consequences where something of value is at stake and where the outcome is uncertain, recognizing the diversity of values. Risk is often represented as probability of occurrence of hazardous events or trends multiplied by the impacts if these events or trends occur. Risk results from the interaction of vulnerability, exposure, and hazard. The term risk is used primarily to refer to the risks of climate-change impacts in the present template.

³⁴ "The Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy Reporting Guidelines" Version 1.0 (June 2016)

Adaptation Process

Risk & Vulnerability Assessment(s) (RVA(s))	Determines the nature and extent of risk by analysing potential hazards and assessing vulnerability that could pose a potential threat or harm to people, property, livelihoods and the environment on which they depend – it allows the identification of areas of critical concern and therefore provides information for decision-making. This can take the form of one assessment, or several assessments undertaken reflecting different local priorities. They can include different types of assessments (for example, institutional risk assessments, hazard assessments, retrospective vulnerability assessments in the case of extreme weather events).
Adaptation Strategy	Outlines the vision of the local authority for a more climate resilient future; Specifies the priority areas of action as well as the mechanisms for stakeholder involvement, funding and resource mobilisation, continuous monitoring and review.
Adaptation Action Plan	Defines a set of concrete adaptation actions, together with time frames and assigned responsibilities, which translate the long-term strategy into action.
Adaptation Actions (or measures)	Technologies, processes, and activities directed at enhancing our capacity to adapt (building adaptive capacity) and at minimising, adjusting to and taking advantage of the consequences of climatic change (delivering adaptation).
Adaptation Option Assessment	The practice of identifying options to adapt to climate change and evaluating them in terms of criteria such as availability, benefits, costs, effectiveness, efficiency and feasibility.
Mainstreaming	Mainstreaming adaptation into policy processes focuses on integrating adaptation issues into other ongoing (sectoral) policy processes.
Evaluation	A process for systematically and objectively determining the effectiveness of an adaptation measure in the light of its objectives.

Climate Hazards

Flood	The overflowing of the normal confines of a stream or other body of water, or the accumulation of water over areas that are not normally submerged. Floods include river (fluvial) floods, flash floods, urban floods, pluvial floods, sewer floods, coastal floods, and glacial lake outburst floods.
Drought	A period of abnormally dry weather long enough to cause a serious hydrological imbalance.
Storm	An atmospheric disturbance that can be manifested in strong winds and accompanied by rain, snow, or other precipitation and by thunder and lightning.

▪ **Sectors**

Buildings	Refers to any (municipal/residential/tertiary, public/private) structure or groups of structures, surrounding spaces, permanently constructed or erected on its site.
Transport	Includes road, rail, air and water transport networks and related infrastructure (e.g. roads, bridges, hubs, tunnels, ports and airports). It comprises an extensive range of both public and private assets and services and excludes all related vessels, vehicles (and related parts and processes).
Energy	Refers to the energy supply service and related infrastructure (generation, transmission & distribution networks, all energy types). It includes coal, crude oil, natural gas liquids, refinery feedstocks, additives, petroleum products, gases, combustible renewables and waste, electricity and heat.
Water	Refers to the water supply service and related infrastructure. It also covers water use (e.g. by households, industry, energy production, agriculture, etc.) and (waste-, rain-) water management system, that includes sewers, drainage and treatment systems (i.e. the process to render waste water fit to meet environmental standards or other quality norms, as well as to cope with excess rain or storm water).
Waste	Includes activities related to the management (including collection, treatment and disposal) of various forms of waste, such as solid or non-solid industrial or household waste, as well as contaminated sites.

Land Use Planning	Process undertaken by public authorities to identify, evaluate and decide on different options for the use of land, including consideration of long term economic, social and environmental objectives and the implications for different communities and interest groups, and the subsequent formulation and promulgation of plans or regulations that describe the permitted or acceptable uses.
Agriculture & Forestry	Includes land classified / designated for agriculture & forestry use, as well as organisations and industries linked to creation and production within and surrounding the boundaries of the municipality. It includes animal husbandry, aquaculture, agroforestry, beekeeping, horticulture and other agriculture & forestry management and services in the area.
Environment & Biodiversity	Environment refers to green and blue landscapes, air quality, including urban hinterland; Biodiversity refers to the variety of life in a specific region, measurable as the variety within species, between species, and the variety of ecosystems.
Health	Refers to the geographical distribution of dominance of pathologies (allergies, cancers, respiratory and heart diseases, etc.), information indicating the effect on health (biomarkers, decline of fertility, epidemics) or well-being of humans (fatigue, stress, post-traumatic stress disorder, death etc.) linked directly (air pollution, heat waves, droughts, severe flood events, ground level ozone, noise, etc.) or indirectly (food / water quality and availability, genetically modified organisms, etc.) to the quality of the environment. It also includes the health care service and related infrastructure (e.g. hospitals).
Civil Protection and Emergency	Refers to the operation of the civil protection and emergency services by or on behalf of public authorities (e.g. civil protection authorities, police, fire-fighters, ambulance, paramedic and emergency medicine services) and includes local disaster risk reduction and management (i.e. capacity building, coordination, equipment, emergency planning etc.).
Tourism	Refers to the activities of persons travelling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes not related to the exercise of an activity remunerated from within the place visited.
Other	Any other sectors (e.g. Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), Industry, Financial)

Annex II – Questionnaire answers from CRISTAL river pilots

Question	French pilot	Polish pilot	Italian pilot (Infrastrutture Venete)	Italian pilot (AIPO)
<p>1. What is considered a disruption, for your business? Make an example of a natural and man-made disruption</p>	<p>Drought, flood, structure failure, navigation incident, technological risk, pollution from stakeholders, computer failure/cybersecurity</p>	<p>An example of a natural disruption would be too high or too low water level. An example of a man-made disruption would be a break in the operation of hydrotechnical infrastructure</p>	<p>Natural = FLOOD and or prolonged DROUGHT. It can happen that the level of water could be too high or low hampering the navigability. Man-made = ACCIDENTS (e.g. something temporarily interrupting the continuity of the waterway function, including the malfunctioning of locks etc) Also water POLLUTION, even if not physically hampering the navigation, could represent a disruption of business as it calls for specific remediations that would limit navigability conditions. In particular, waste floating/not floating material can hamper navigability or correct functioning of locks</p>	<p>Natural = FLOOD and or prolonged DROUGHT Man-made = ACCIDENTS (e.g. something temporarily interrupting the continuity of the waterway function, including the malfunctioning of locks etc) Also water POLLUTION, even if not physically hampering the navigation, could represent a disruption of business as it calls for specific remediations that would limit navigability conditions</p>

<p>2. Are you able to monetize the impact of at least one past disruption?</p>	<p>Orders of magnitude of impacts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Each year in France, floods cause approximately €700 million in damage (first natural risk, one third of the municipalities exposed) according to INRAE - Seine flood type 1910: 30 billion euros in damage estimated by the OECD if such a flood were to occur today - Seine et Loing flood of May/June 2016: property damage of €1 billion (200,000 claims); emergency plan for the rehabilitation of the infrastructure by VNF: €10 million of work - Seine flood January/February 2018: property damage of €150 million (35,000 claims) - 2018 failure of the Vives-Eaux site on the upstream Seine (failure of the dam + flood + failure of the main lock then of the two locks): payment by VNF of €800,000 in compensation 	<p>No such analyses have been carried out in my company, but it can be concluded that the impact on monetary losses would be negligible. This is due to the low traffic on the waterway</p>	<p>Not applicable. In any case, through apposite CBA it could be possible to compare the avoided benefits with additional costs of other alternatives</p>	<p>Not applicable. In any case, through apposite CBA it could be possible to compare the avoided benefits with additional costs of other alternatives</p>
---	--	---	---	---

	<p>(100 files) to the carriers affected</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aude October 2018 floods: €200 million in damage to property for insurance companies + €70 million in damage to uninsured property of local authorities - April 2021 cyberattack: €350,000 + 400 man-days for analysis and return to normal + €120,000/year for new permanent IT security services 			
<p>3. Are you subject to contractual penalties, in case you are not able to run your business for a while?</p>	<p>In France, when a river stretch is made unavailable by some unexpected event, ship-owners may claim for financial compensations from VNF. There is a specific scheme based upon precise daily rates, depending on the type of barge used</p>		<p>No, even if operators would potentially ask for some refunds if services are not appropriately provided</p>	<p>No, even if operators would potentially ask for some refunds if services are not appropriately provided</p>
<p>4. Can you define the lowest level of the service(s) you provide, you would like to maintain even during a disruption?</p>	<p>No minimum service in case of disruption. Double locks at certain dams to limit the risk of navigation stops</p>	<p>On rivers not regulated by barrages, we would like to maintain the declared level of waterway class for more than 240 days a year (Ordinance on the classification of inland waterways)</p>	<p>It obviously depends on the type of criticality/damage/disruption. Potentially the navigability should be simply maintained, if possible, even if with</p>	<p>It obviously depends on the type of criticality/damage/disruption. Potentially the navigability should be simply maintained, if possible, even if with reduced availability</p>

			reduced availability even with longest transit-time for locks	
5. Can you list critical assets, operations and systems? They are defined as the essential assets, operations and systems to deliver your (core) service(s)	VNF is an operator of vital importance: VNF manages critical infrastructures identified by the government for security reasons. In addition, some hydraulic structures are subject to specific regulations on their safety given the risks for the population in the event of the rupture of these structures. No specific classification of critical works, operations and systems for the essential services provided by VNF		There are no specific critical assets as far as the maintenance and functionality of the entire network is potentially compromised by the crash of a single node/dock/lock. In this purpose, all of the assets composing the network (infrastructures, locks, ICT system ...) are essential for a fully functional IWW. In case of malfunctioning of remote control of the locks, a dedicated team is sent to operate manually the service	The critical assets of IWW managed by AIPO is compromised both by high or low water level because the Po River is a free-flowing river and by the interruption of the connection with inland ports or artificial channels
6. Can you assess criticality for your assets, operations and systems? Follow the table below	VNF has a mapping of budgetary and accounting risks that is regularly updated, with the following objectives: - identify the risks to which VNF is exposed in order to anticipate those that may affect the activity and the strategic objectives of the Establishment.		SAFETY / Moderate ECONOMIC / Major PUBLIC EFFECTS / Minor ENVIRONMENTAL / Moderate	SAFETY / Minor ECONOMIC / Major PUBLIC EFFECTS / Major ENVIRONMENTAL / Minor

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - assess the current level of control based on the best practices encountered in VNF's business sector, according to its strategic objectives - prioritize the implementation of the necessary control elements in order to significantly reduce current exposures and enable the achievement of strategic objectives. <p>The structures are assessed with a functional condition index.</p> <p>There is no specific, formalized and regularly updated national analysis of the criticality of VNF assets, operations and systems</p>			
<p>7. What are the natural and man-made impacts that can affect your critical assets? Can you determine their likelihood (based on historical data or future projections)?</p>	<p>See question 1 for the list of hazards that can affect our critical assets. See question 6 for the probability: we do not have these probabilities specifically for our critical assets but we have knowledge of return times for floods (excluding the impact of climate change) and the history of</p>	<p>In my opinion, from the point of view of the waterway administrator, factors of natural origin may be a flood or a hydrological drought. They can be predicted by analysing historical data</p>	<p>See the examples provided in point 1 and 6. No particular database is currently available on such kind of data</p>	<p>See the examples provided in point 1 and 6. We have historical data concerning navigability along the Po River</p>

	<p>water reserves for droughts (including reservoir dams managed by VNF). According to the central reinsurance fund (annual report published on March 15, 2023), the historic drought of 2003 could see its return period drop from 15 years to 7 years</p>			
<p>8. Can you link impacts with monitorable parameters? Do you have monitoring systems/can you access relevant external data for those parameters?</p>	<p>VNF has internal and external data but does not have internal models</p>	<p>Yes, it can be linked together. I have access to a water level monitoring system</p>	<p>Potentially the answer is yes, but according to detailed study/analysis to be compared with collected data on a long term basis. In this purpose, it is here to be mentioned that IV is operational only since 2020 so not necessarily able to collect historic data on all the IWW. However, even if data are available since 2015 on water levels, IV is currently working on the adoption of appropriate system to record and monitor them which is not yet functional</p>	<p>The answer is yes, in according to detailed study/analysis to be compared with collected data on a long term basis. We still have water level monitoring system and in CRISTAL we would merge monitoring data with statistical analysis for navigability</p>
<p>9. Are you able to define thresholds for monitored parameters, beyond which</p>	<p>If the continuity of river transport is interrupted for more than 4 hours on the large</p>	<p>For example, high navigable water above which navigation is prohibited</p>	<p>If the interruption is expected for more than one day, then</p>	<p>We can define thresholds for low and high-water level/discharge. The first one</p>

<p>you expect an unacceptable impact on your assets, operations or systems?</p>	<p>gauge and more than 24 hours on the small gauge, it is up to VNF to plan an intervention procedure and to take certain measures.</p> <p>Navigation requires monitoring the guaranteed anchorage (service level) between a minimum and a maximum acceptable for navigation (a boat must not touch the bottom of the waterway or under a bridge), as well as the minimum biological flows natural waterways.</p>	<p>(WWŻ in Polish). Transit depth reports are also posted online for waterways with particular indication of places limiting navigation</p>	<p>alternative options are put in place/communicated</p>	<p>is defined by the hull immersing and the second one depends on the geometrical dimension of infrastructures (i.e., bridge vertical clearance)</p>
<p>10. Do you have plans/procedures if threshold levels are exceeded?</p>	<p>When a disruption in the IWW occurs VNF territorial management immediately inform the users by Notices to Skippers. The shipper's dispatch department receives the information that the inland waterways is not available for an estimated time of (...). They forward the information to other departments within the company, so that they can arrange other ways of moving the cargo (generally speaking,</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>As mentioned in the previous questionnaire, the following steps are foreseen in case of disruptive events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. IV send via radio a direct info to the ships that are currently using the infrastructure; ii. IV send an e-mail to a specific mailing list including several stakeholders and users to inform about the disruptive event; 	<p>As mentioned in the previous questionnaire, the following steps are foreseen in case of disruptive events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. AIPO send an e-mail to a specific mailing list including several stakeholders and users to inform about the disruptive event. ii. In case of serious events which causes the need to stop navigation, AIPO informs the appropriate

	<p>road transport). Then, they charter the required number of trucks to move the cargo to the consignee(s)</p>		<p>iii. In case of serious events which causes the need to stop navigation, IV informs the appropriate “Ispettorato di porto” (i.e. the regional offices formally in charge of functionality and supervision of inland navigation and lakes which are distributed for Province)</p> <p>iv. “Ispettorato di porto” launches specific dispatches (i.e. “Ordinanza”) giving formal stop to navigation on the specific section of the IWW.</p> <p>v. in case of particular circumstances, also the website of IV is going to be updated with detailed info on the navigability conditions.</p> <p>vi. Once the problem is solved, another “Ordinanza” is issued thus allowing once again the navigation of the limited navigation (i.e. “Avviso Cauta Navigazione”)</p>	<p>“Ispettorato di porto del Fiume Po”.</p> <p>iii. “Ispettorato di porto” launches specific dispatches (i.e. “Ordinanza”) giving formal stop to navigation on the specific section of the IWW.</p> <p>iv. The website of AIPo is going to be updated with detailed info on the navigability conditions.</p> <p>v. Once the problem is solved, another “Ordinanza” is issued thus allowing once again the navigation of the limited navigation (i.e. “Avviso Cauta Navigazione”)</p>
<p>11. Do you have an inventory of past disruptions?</p>	<p>The report has been established of an increase in the</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>See answer 7 and 8. Moreover, there is a</p>	<p>See answer 7 and 8. Yes</p>

	<p>number and frequency of floods occurring on the river network since 2016 of a level of severity that allows them to be qualified as a crisis: Loing floods in June 2016; Meuse floods in November-December 2017; floods of the Yonne, the Seine, the Meuse, the Marne, the Rhône and the Rhine from January to February 2018; Aude floods in November 2018 and October 2019.</p> <p>VNF does not have an incident database but does have a database of Notices to Skippers and a national network availability indicator.</p>		<p>recording (per year) or decrees issued with reference of such happenings</p>	
<p>12. Do you already have in place adaptation measures for short/long term climate/man-made impacts?</p>	<p>Business continuity plan: on-call, crisis organization, exercises, feedback</p> <p>Low water level: setting up a watch and alert position, user information, proactive communication, hydraulic management and biodiversity protection measures, harmonization of crisis management practices,</p>	<p>They are in preparation</p>	<p>Not yet, a part from the interventions currently ongoing or planned in terms of upgrading of the infrastructure, including the technological equipment expected through the development of cold ironing facilities (as an answer to alternative solutions of mobility)</p>	<p>Not yet</p>

	modernization of the network, development of water management skills. the water Investment in infrastructure rehabilitation and modernization			
--	--	--	--	--

Implications for: Scale of impact:	Safety	Economic effects; business continuity	Public effects and local community	Environment sustainability and compliance	Critical?
Catastrophic	Risk of large numbers of serious injuries or loss of life	Loss or degradation would risk long-term viability of business including supply chains	Essential services lost, daily life becomes intolerable, unacceptable physical suffering	Irrecoverable damage, proven breach, prospect of corporate penalty	Yes
Major	Risk of isolated instances of serious injuries or loss of life	Loss or degradation would have serious effects on business requiring significant remedial action	Severe disruption of essential services and hence daily life, high levels of physical suffering	Severe and continuing loss, significant management effort needed to deal with compliance failure	Probably
Moderate	Risk of small numbers of injuries	Intervention needed to protect business continuity	Frequent disruption of essential services; daily life difficult, moderate levels of physical suffering	Minor, reversible damage, action needed on issues of compliance	Unlikely
Minor or insignificant	Risk of near misses or minor injuries	Isolated difficulties (e.g. in supply chain, replacements or alternatives exist)	Intermittent disruption of essential services and daily life, low levels of physical suffering	Negligible damage, minor breaches, easily resolved	Not critical

Table 3: Example considerations for determining criticality

Figure 6 Example considerations for determining critical

11. List of tables

Table 1 Alignment of D3.2 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable and task(s) descriptions	8
Table 2 Overview of European Legislation on sustainable development and ESG strategy	14
Table 3 Common structure of a management system	17
Table 4 Groups of indicators analysed in ISO 37123 related to all possible environmental, social and governance risks.....	19
Table 5 Contribution of synchromodality to BCM	60

12. List of figures

Figure 1 Illustration of the core concept of risk (AR5), based on IPCC AR5.....	24
Figure 2 Scheme representing a virtuous cycle where each action strengthens the organization and the community to conduct to sustainable development	28
Figure 3 The seven core-subjects of ISO 26000:2010.....	29
Figure 5 A typical GHG project cycle	37
Figure 6 Relationship between key terms	43
Figure 7 Example considerations for determining critical	79